

Report on CHPM process optimisation

CHPM2030 Deliverable D4.2

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CHPM2030

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CHPM2030

CHPM2030 DELIVERABLE D4.2

REPORT ON CHPM PROCESS OPTIMISATION

Summary:

This deliverable describes the computer model that has been developed to simulate the integrated CHPM2030 metal extraction and electricity generation system. The individual technical components are described as well as the methodology to develop mathematical description of their performance and how they are combined in an integrated system. A probabilistic approach is used to estimate the input parameters as well as the simulation results. The model is used on five scenarios to evaluate the performance of selected geothermal sites in Europe. The performance of each of these sites is simulated and sensitivity analysis presented.

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Table of contents

Table of contents.....	2
LIST OF FIGURES	3
LIST OF TABLES	6
1 Executive summary	8
2 Introduction.....	9
3 Description of the components of the CHPM system.....	9
3.1 Geothermal reservoir and production/injection wells	10
3.2 Electrolytic metal recovery	10
3.3 Binary power plant and heat generation.....	13
3.4 Gas diffusion electro-crystallisation (GDEx)	14
3.5 Salinity gradient power through reverse electrodialysis (SGP-RE)	18
4 Methodology	20
4.1 Component models	24
4.1.1 Component model for electrolytic metal recovery	24
4.1.2 Component model for combined heat and power production	25
4.1.3 Component model for the gas diffusion electro-crystallisation metal extraction (GDEx)	27
4.1.4 Component model for salinity gradient power (SGP-RE)	32
4.2 System modelling tools	36
5 Results.....	38
5.1 Reykjanes brine scenario.....	40
5.2 Landau brine scenario	46
5.3 Balmatt brine scenario	52
5.4 Cornwall brine scenario.....	58
5.5 Romanian brine scenario.....	64
5.6 Sensitivity analysis	70
6 Conclusions.....	75
7 References.....	76
Appendix A: GDEx data	78
Appendix B: Model distribution around each sample	80

LIST OF FIGURES

<i>Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the overall CHPM system showing the links between the different components.</i>	9
<i>Figure 2. CHPM schematics, 2019 (©CHPM2030 Team)</i>	10
<i>Figure 3. (A) Cross-sectional view of ETPER manufactured (B) High temperature and pressure rotating disk electrode designed to operate at 200 bar and 300°C.</i>	11
<i>Figure 4. Schematic diagram of a geothermal binary cycle power plant.</i>	13
<i>Figure 5. Schematic outline of geothermal CHP configurations. The red lines represent the geothermal brine (from Van Erdeweghe et al., 2018).</i>	14
<i>Figure 6. Schematic diagram of the gas diffusion electro-crystallisation (GDEx) technology for the treatment of geothermal brines.</i>	15
<i>Figure 7. Flow diagrams of the GDEx technology and peripheral processing units for geothermal brines.</i>	18
<i>Figure 8. Schematic drawing of reverse electrodialysis.</i>	19
<i>Figure 9. Schematic presentation of a component model.</i>	21
<i>Figure 10. Log scale concentration for various metals in brine samples from the Western part of the US (red and orange) and from the Reykjanes geothermal area in Iceland (blue). The US samples are brine samples from the USGS open file database for geothermal brines which are over 100°C. The right axis denotes the number of US samples that contained the metals shown on the left axis. For the US samples red denotes concentrations within in the 25% to 75% percentile range and orange outside.</i>	22
<i>Figure 11. (a) Input probability distribution for temperature for the binary power plant component. (b) Output probability distribution for power production for the binary power plant component.</i>	23
<i>Figure 12. Relation between energy use of the Gas diffusion electro-precipitation component as a function of (a) Mg concentration and (b) salinity.</i>	23
<i>Figure 13. Component model output for the final concentration (dashed red lines show 95% confidence interval) and results of the experiments at 150°C, 50 bar, at a potential of 500 mV vs Pt (quasi reversible electrode) to reduce Cu from the brine (blue dots).</i>	25
<i>Figure 14. Demand profile for a district heating system with an annual heat consumption of 10,000 MWh.</i>	26
<i>Figure 15. Comparison of the calibrated model for the energy input per extracted metal mass (Equation 13) and measured values.</i>	30
<i>Figure 16. Comparison of the calibrated model for the ratio of extracted Al and measured values.</i>	31
<i>Figure 17. Comparison of the calibrated model for the ratio of extracted Li and measured values.</i>	31
<i>Figure 18. Comparison of the calibrated model for the ratio of extracted (a) Sr, (b) Mn, (c) Ba, (d) As, (e) Zn, (f) Rb, and (g) Ni and measured values.</i>	32
<i>Figure 19. Simulating model for one cell pair in a stack with n cell pairs.</i>	33
<i>Figure 20. Powerplot simulation results (2M vs 0,02M NaCl, 50°C, 100m³/h).</i>	36
<i>Figure 21. Schematics of the Monte Carlo model.</i>	37

Figure 22. Probability distributions for the input parameters for the Reykjanes brine: (a) salinity (b) pH. The distributions were constructed from 10,000 random realizations of the input parameters. 40

Figure 23. Probability distributions of metal extractions by the electrolysis component from the Reykjanes brine for (a) Copper, (b) Arsenic, (c) Silver, (d) Antimony, and (e) Gold. 42

Figure 24. The four most extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Reykjanes brine: (a) Iron, (b) Bromine, (c) Zink, and (d) Copper. 43

Figure 25. Resulting distributions for the Reykjanes site: (a) the power input for the electrolysis component, (b) the power output of the geothermal power plant, (c) the power input for the gas diffusion component, (d) the power output of the salt gradient power component, and (e) the net electric power balance of the whole CHPM system. 44

Figure 26. Summary of the model results for a theoretical CHMP-plant based on the characteristics of the Reykjanes brine. 45

Figure 27. Probability distributions for the input parameters for the Landau brine: (a) salinity, (b) temperature, (c) flow rate and (d) pH. The distributions were constructed from 10,000 random realizations of the input parameters..... 47

Figure 28. Probability distributions of metal extractions by the electrolysis component from the Landau brine for (a) Arsenic and (b) Copper. 48

Figure 29. The four most extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Landau brine: (a) Strotium, (b) Bromium, (c) Lithium, and (d) Iron. 49

Figure 30. Resulting distributions for the Landau site: (a) the power input for the electrolysis component, (b) the power output of the geothermal power plant, (c) the power input for the gas diffusion component, (d) the power output of the salt gradient power component, and (e) the net electric power balance of the whole CHPM system. 50

Figure 31. Summary of the model results for a theoretical CHMP-plant based on the characteristics of the Landau brine. 51

Figure 32. Probability distributions for the input parameters for the Balmatt brine: (a) salinity, (b) temperature, (c) flow rate and (d) pH. The distributions were constructed from 10,000 random realizations of the input parameters..... 53

Figure 33. Probability distributions of metal extraction by the electrolysis component from the Balmatt brine for copper..... 54

Figure 34. The four most extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Balmatt brine: (a) Iron, (b) Strontium, (c) Bromine, and (d) Barium. 55

Figure 35. Resulting distributions for the Balmatt site: (a) the power input for the electrolysis component, (b) the power output of the geothermal power plant, (c) the power input for the gas diffusion component, (d) the power output of the salt gradient power component, and (e) the net electric power balance of the whole CHPM system. 56

Figure 36. Summary of the model results for a theoretical CHMP-plant based on the characteristics of the Balmatt brine. 57

Figure 37. Probability distributions for the input parameters for the Cornwall brine: (a) salinity, (b) temperature, (c) flow rate and (d) pH. The distributions were constructed from 10,000 random realizations of the input parameters..... 59

Figure 38. Probability distributions of metal extraction by the electrolysis component from the Cornwall brine for copper..... 60

Figure 39. The four most extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Cornwall brine: (a) Lithium, (b) Strontium, (c) Boron, and (d) Manganese..... 61

Figure 40. Resulting distributions for the Cornwall site: (a) the power input for the electrolysis component, (b) the power output of the geothermal power plant, (c) the power input for the gas diffusion component, (d) the power output of the salt gradient power component, and (e) the net electric power balance of the whole CHPM system. 62

Figure 41. Summary of the model results for a theoretical CHMP-plant based on the characteristics of the Cornwall brine. 63

Figure 42. Probability distributions for the input parameters for the Romanian brine: (a) salinity, (b) temperature, (c) flow rate and (d) pH. The distributions were constructed from 10,000 random realizations of the input parameters. 65

Figure 43. Probability distribution of metal extraction by the electrolysis component from the Romanian brine for copper..... 66

Figure 44. The four most extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Romanian brine: (a) Strontium, (b) Barium, (c) Zinc, and (d) Iron. 67

Figure 45. Resulting distributions for the Romanian site: (a) the power input for the electrolysis component, (b) the power output of the geothermal power plant, (c) the power input for the gas diffusion component, (d) the power output of the salt gradient power component, and (e) the net electric power balance of the whole CHPM system. 68

Figure 46. Summary of the model results for a theoretical CHMP-plant based on the characteristics of the Romanian brine..... 69

Figure 47. Pseudocode of the sensitivity analysis. 70

Figure 48. Sensitivity of the power consumption of the electrolysis component to small change in (a) pH, (b) pressure, (c) flow rate, (d) salinity, (e) temperature. The fixed parameter values are taken from the most likely or average values of the Landau scenario. 71

Figure 49. Sensitivity of the power production of the geothermal power plant to small change in (a) pH, (b) pressure, (c) flow rate, (d) salinity, (e) temperature. The fixed parameter values are taken from the most likely or average values of the Landau scenario. 72

Figure 50. Sensitivity of the power consumption of the gas diffusion component to small change in (a) pH, (b) pressure, (c) flow rate, (d) salinity, (e) temperature. The fixed parameter values are taken from the most likely or average values of the Landau scenario. 73

Figure 51. Sensitivity of the power production of the salt gradient component to small change in (a) pH, (b) pressure, (c) flow rate, (d) salinity, (e) temperature. The fixed parameter values are taken from the most likely or average values of the Landau scenario. 74

Figure 52. Sensitivity of the net power of whole CHPM loop to small change in (a) pH, (b) pressure, (c) flow rate, (d) salinity, (e) temperature. The fixed parameter values are taken from the most likely or average values of the Landau scenario. 75

Figure 53. Distributions of calculated energy per kg of extracted metal in kWh/kg and measured energy values of extracted of metal for each sample. These distributions are also shown in Figure 15. 80

Figure 54. Distributions of calculated ratios of Al metal extracted and measured values for each sample. These distributions are also shown in Figure 16. 81

Figure 55. Distributions of calculated ratios of Li metal extracted and measured values for each sample. These distributions are also shown in Figure 17. 81

Figure 56. Uniform distributions of calculated ratios of Sr, Mn, Ba, As, Zn, Rb, and Ni extracted and measured values for each sample. These distributions are also shown in Figure 18. 82

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Experimental conditions (high and low) for parameters evaluated in the study. 12

Table 2. Recovery of Cu and energy consumption at 150°C, 50 bar and a potential of 500 mV vs Pt as a function of initial concentration (C_{in}). 24

Table 3. Model parameters for the energy input per kg of extracted metal found in Equation 13 according to the linear regression analysis. 28

Table 4. Regression parameters for the ratios of extracted Al and Li found in Equation 16 and Equation 17, respectively. 29

Table 5. Overview of the simulation results (2M vs 0.02M NaCl, 50°C, 100m³/h). 35

Table 6. Summary of the model results for the selected scenarios. 39

Table 7. Input parameters representing brine from the Reykjanes geothermal area. 41

Table 8. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the electrolysis component from the Reykjanes brine for Copper, Arsenic, Silver, Antimony, and Gold. 42

Table 9. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Reykjanes brine. 43

Table 10. Mean power produced or consumed by components in CHPM plant for the Reykjanes site. 45

Table 11. Input parameters representing brine from the Landau geothermal area. 47

Table 12. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the electrolysis component from the Landau brine for arsenic and copper. 48

Table 13. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Landau brine. 49

Table 14. Mean power produced or consumed by components in CHPM plant for the Landau site. 50

Table 15. Input parameters representing brine from the Balmatt geothermal area. 53

Table 16. Mean values for the amount of extracted metal by the electrolysis component from the Balmatt brine for copper...... 54

Table 17. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Balmatt brine...... 55

Table 18. Mean power produced or consumed by components in CHPM plant for the Balmatt site. 56

Table 19. Input parameters representing brine from the Cornwall geothermal area...... 59

Table 20. Mean values for the amount of extracted metal by the electrolysis component from the Cornwall brine for copper...... 60

Table 21. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Cornwall brine...... 61

Table 22. Mean power produced or consumed by components in CHPM plant for the Cornwall site. 62

Table 23. Input parameters representing brine from the Romanian geothermal area. 65

Table 24. Mean values for the amount of extracted metal by the electrolysis component from the Romanian brine for copper...... 66

Table 25. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Romanian brine...... 67

Table 26. Mean power produced or consumed by components in CHPM plant for the Romanian site. 68

Table 27. Data used in calibration of the gas diffusion electroprecipitation model. 78

Table 28: Concentrations and extraction ratios of metals other than Li and Al in the Romanian brine samples as presented in deliverable 3.2. 79

1 Executive summary

The aim of the system integration work package is to combine the different processes included in the CHPM2030 project into a single system and develop a computer model for simulation of the overall metal extraction and electricity and heat production processes. The relevant surface components are: (1) electrolytic metal recovery, (2) geothermal binary power plant, (3) heat utilisation, (4) gas diffusion electro-precipitation metal extraction and (5) salt gradient power generation. The basis for the system integration is mathematical description of the behaviour of the individual components, so-called sub-models, resulting from laboratory tests and other work done in the project on specific technical components. The main model parameters are fluid temperature, salinity, flow rate and concentration of different metals. The sub-models are linked together to describe the overall system performance. A probabilistic approach is used by applying Monte Carlo simulation technique to consider the uncertainties of the input parameters, resulting in a probability distribution of the calculated output values. The overall model can be used to study different scenarios and perform simulations, optimisation and other kinds of system analysis. Within the CHPM2030 project the model has been tested on five different European geothermal fields by evaluating the amount of metal that can be extracted as well as the amount of energy generated or consumed by the individual components. Sensitivity analysis have also been performed to estimate the influence of different parameters on the final model results.

2 Introduction

The main objective of the CHPM2030 project is to develop a novel technological solution (Combined Heat, Power and Metal extraction from ultra deep ore bodies), which may help reducing Europe's dependency on the import of metals and fossil fuels, and at the same time, lower the environmental impact of the energy supply. In the envisioned technology, an Enhanced Geothermal System (EGS) is established on a metal-bearing geological formation, which will be manipulated in a way that the co-production of energy and metals will be possible.

The project, at a laboratory scale, intends to prove the concept that the composition and structure of ore bodies have certain characteristics that could be used as an advantage when developing an EGS. The main objective of the system integration work package is to integrate downstream and upstream processes into a single system for energy and metals production and to analyse the model results to assist in identifying the most feasible structure of the overall system. This task combines the experience of the consortium members with the design of medium and high-enthalpy geothermal systems and the project outcomes to create novel technology that will produce energy and valuable metals in an interlinked process. This knowledge will be utilised to adapt contemporary power plant design to the expected temperature and extreme salinity conditions that will occur under the CHPM2030 scheme.

3 Description of the components of the CHPM system

The schematic diagram of the overall CHPM system, shown in Figure 1, was developed at an early stage of the project. It shows the different components of a CHPM-plant in a logical sequence that is based on the optimal operational conditions for the different technologies. Based on the results of the CHPM2030 project, a much more flexible set-up is envisioned for future CHPM-plants. The technologies that will be applied will depend on the characteristics of the brine and needs. Likewise, the position of the technologies may be shifted. A different version of the schematic presentation of the current CHPM system is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the overall CHPM system showing the links between the different components.

Figure 2. CHPM schematics, 2019 (©CHPM2030 Team)

To give an idea of the function of the main components in the system they are briefly described in the following sub-chapters.

3.1 Geothermal reservoir and production/injection wells

In principle, the geothermal reservoir (No. 1 in Figure 1) as well as the production and reinjection wells (No. 2 and 3 in Figure 1) are components that could be described mathematically in a similar way as other components in the system. In the development of the current integrated system the focus has been on the surface components and therefore the reservoir and the wells are not described by separate component models. This is a separate task that must consider the complexity of these components. They can be added in further studies if desired by building on already existing research and modelling of reservoirs and geothermal wells. The current system model uses fluid properties at the production wellhead as input. These are based on reservoir properties from known geothermal fields.

3.2 Electrolytic metal recovery

The Electrolytic metal recovery component (No. 3 in Figure 1) uses electrochemical reactions to deposit metals. The component is designed to perform at high temperatures, 300°C, and high pressures up to 200 bar. The working electrode design is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. (A) Cross-sectional view of ETPEP manufactured (B) High temperature and pressure rotating disk electrode designed to operate at 200 bar and 300°C.

The lab experiments performed in the context of CHPM2030 are performed in small batch reactors. In order to be applicable in a geothermal plant, the technology needs to be scaled by a factor of $10^4 - 10^6$. Preferably, the electrolytic metal deposition technology is implemented in a flow-through reactor that can be readily integrated in a geothermal loop with a high throughput (150 m³/h or more).

The main objective of the project was to evaluate the feasibility and develop a model for the optimized metal recovery from geothermal brines, via electrodeposition at elevated temperature and elevated pressure, from a systems integration perspective. As a part of this objective, our tasks were divided into: (1) Developing thermodynamic models for several metals at 150°C and 50 bar. This will aid in the identification of the reduction potential for several metals at high temperature and pressure. (2) Engineering design of the reactor, which encompasses the development of a process flow diagram and a safety analysis of the same. (3) Effect of various operating conditions on the recovery rate, efficiency, and energy required for metal removal was investigated with Cu as the sample species. The effect of silica on the metal recovery was also studied.

The thermodynamic potential-pH diagrams were modelled for the following system Cu, Pb, Ni, Ag, Sn, and Zn at (1) 25°C and 1 bar; (2) 25°C and 50 bar and (3) 150°C and 50 bar. The aim was to determine how the oxidation states and reduction potentials of the metals vary with temperature and pressure.

An ETEP – Rotating electrode reactor system was designed and constructed to perform electrodeposition of the geothermal brines at high temperature and high pressure. The description of the reactor system along with the process flow diagram and details for material selection are presented in the deliverable D3.1. Risk analyses and safety tests was performed for the system. Details of process flow diagram and risk analyses are included in deliverable D3.1.

Recovery rate and efficiency of metal recovery for geothermal brines were selected as the primary indices for measuring the performance of the system. A One Factor at a Time (OFAT) design of experiment was carried out to study the effect of parameters on the primary indices. The major parameters that were selected to study the influence on metal recovery for this study were: (1) temperature, (2) pressure, (3) initial concentration, (4) potential applied, and (5) silica content.

Experiments were carried out with the elevated temperature elevated pressure (ETEP) rotating electrode reactor (RER) built as a part of this project. Reticulated Vitreous Carbon (RVC) was used as the substrate, Pt-Rh gauze was used as the counter electrode, and mesoporous Pt was used as a pseudoreference electrode. More details on the material selection for the reactor, substrate, reference electrode, and counter electrode are explained in D3.1. Details of the experimental matrix for this study is listed in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Experimental conditions (high and low) for parameters evaluated in the study.

	Temp (°C)	Pressure (bar)	Cu conc. (mM)	E (mV) vs mPt	Time (min)
Low	25	1	1	-450	30
High	150	50	10	-700	60

It was shown that the high temperatures allowed for enhanced recovery of copper when compared to the recovery at room temperature. On the other hand pressure did not have any influence on the recovery of copper. At 150°C and 50 bar, maximum recovery rate was obtained for brine containing at least 5 mM Cu and -575 mV vs Pt pseudo reference electrode after 1 hour of deposition.

The major parameter that was found to influence the metal recovery rate and specific energy required for metal recovery was the initial concentration. The recovery rate was directly proportional to the initial concentration, whereas the energy requirement for metal recovery was inversely related to the initial metal concentration in the solution. Additionally, increasing the temperature increases the mass transfer coefficient by 3 times, compared to the recovery studies at room temperature and pressure. The results of this study are set to be published in two peer-reviewed articles in the Journal of Applied Electrochemistry.

It was also found that brine containing SiO₂ with metal (Cu) ratio of 0.25 resulted in deposits containing at least 3% silica. Thus, indicating that this technology, with the current know-how, is suitable for recovery where the silica to metal ratio is less than 0.25 to achieve metal recovery without interference from silica co-deposition. For brines rich in silica and above 100°C, prior to electrodeposition, the brine must be vaporized upon lowering the pressure by passing the stream to a flash drum. This would result in the simultaneous precipitation of any silica which can be separated with an outlet at the bottom of the vessel. The heavy metals precipitated with silica can be extracted by acid leaching as in a mining process, followed by electrodeposition from the metal concentrated leachate solution.

One of the major challenges encountered during this process were mainly pertaining to experimental difficulty. Specifically, maintaining the electrical contact always during the experiment between the rotating electrode inside the pressure chamber and connector pins outside the reactor.

The next steps in this research will include the recovery studies in an ETEP electrochemical hydrocyclone reactor (EHCR) to study the recovery of metals on a continuous basis. Apart from offering a setup with no moving parts, the ETEP-EHCR also allows the recovery on a continuous basis. To evaluate the metal recovery from neutral geothermal brines, a complete parametric study should be performed on the EHCR, prior to the

construction of a pilot reactor. In addition to the parametric study the effect of anions and secondary metal cations on the metal recovery at high temperature must be studied. The energy requirement for metal recovery (g/Wh) is required to estimate the amount of energy required for the recovery of the metals. The optimal temperature and pressure for maximum metal recovery is estimated.

3.3 Binary power plant and heat generation

Geothermal binary cycle power plants (ORC - Organic Rankine Cycle) (No. 4 in Figure 1) are commonly used when the temperature of the geothermal resource is not sufficient for water flash systems, typically in the range 120-180°C. It uses a closed loop working fluid with lower boiling point than water that is vaporised using the heat from the geothermal fluid. The geothermal fluid releases its heat to the working fluid in a heat exchanger before it is reinjected to the reservoir. A schematic diagram of a geothermal binary cycle power plant is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of a geothermal binary cycle power plant.

Different set-ups are possible for combined power and heat generation. In most cases, a binary system is used for power production in geothermal CHP-plants. Different set-ups are possible for delivering heat as shown in Figure 5. The optimal set-up depends on the temperature and energy output of the geothermal wells and the requirements of heat supply (temperature range and demand curve).

Figure 5. Schematic outline of geothermal CHP configurations. The red lines represent the geothermal brine (from Van Erdeeweghe et al., 2018).

3.4 Gas diffusion electro-crystallisation (GDEx)

Gas Diffusion Electro-crystallisation (GDEx) (No. 5 in Figure 1) can remove metal and metalloid ions from an aqueous solution, transforming them into an amorphous or crystalline (nano) precipitate which can be easily recovered by sedimentation. The process uses porous activated carbon-based gas-diffusion electrodes, through which an oxidant gas is passed. The oxidant gas is electrochemically reduced at the cathode, forming reactive intermediaries depending on the gas chosen. For instance, by imposing specific cathodic polarization conditions (e.g., $-0.350 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$), O_2 is electro-reduced, to H_2O_2 in a 2 electron (2 e^-) transfer process and H_2O in a 4 electron (4 e^-) transfer process, as per the following reactions:

By changing the polarization conditions (e.g., $-1.4 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$), CO_2 is electroreduced. CO_2 reduction in aqueous medium, under the experimental conditions of GDEx, can typically result in the formation of carbon monoxide, methanol, formic acid, or methane, via 2 routes and accounting for the following intermediaries (excluding the case of methane):

Route 1

Route 2

Whereas the peroxides issued from O_2 reduction act as oxidizing agents, the products from CO_2 reduction act as reducing agents. Although the specific nature of the CO_2 reduction intermediaries is unclear at present, their reaction with certain soluble metal ions results in third reduction to their elemental form (e.g., Cu, Pt, Pd, Rh, Au). Conversely, the peroxides lead to the formation of oxides and hydroxides, wherein mixed metal oxides are included. Not only these reactive intermediaries accumulate at the electrochemical interface, but also OH^- which also results from the electrochemical reductions. Altogether, this led to progressive changes on the pH and redox potential of the solution, which confined at the thin electrochemical interface lead to the eventual crystallization or precipitation of composites between the metal ions and the oxidant-gas-reduction-product. The precipitate is subsequently released into the aqueous electrolyte where it remains stable in a colloidal form during a certain period, but ultimately aggregates and precipitates. By varying the parameters of the electrochemical process, such as pH, ionic strength, metal/metalloid ion concentration, gas composition and electrochemical potential, not only selectivity can be tuned but also important properties of the product may be controlled such as morphology, particle size, crystal size and lattice parameter. The experimental setup for the component is shown in Figure 6, exemplified with the use of O_2 as the oxidant gas.

Figure 6. Schematic diagram of the gas diffusion electro-crystallisation (GDEX) technology for the treatment of geothermal brines.

The GDEX process is particularly efficient to remove dilute metal ions from solution, preferably in the range of 100 mg/L to 10 g/L. Although it is possible to recover metals in lower concentrations, for fundamental research at lab scale lower concentrations often provide insufficient sample sizes of the products formed for a reliable analysis.

One of the most important advantages of the GDEX process is that no chemical additives need to be provided to the system. All the necessary reagents are produced in-situ in minimal quantities to achieve the targeted transformations. A secondary benefit is that the energy input required to operate the system is minimal, making its operational costs much lower than other available technologies. Although the GDEX process could operate at high-temperature and high-pressure conditions, the current electrochemical reactors build for the experimental assessment of this process only allow operating at atmospheric pressure and temperature up to 70°C.

Operational parameters

Several operational parameters are relevant for the successful and optimized operation of the GDEX process. Some of the most important ones are the following:

- Nature and concentration of metal ions. It is proven feasible that the GDEX process can effectively recover: Lu, Al, Ar, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Y, Rh, Pd, Pt, Au, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Er. There are some difficulties to recover B. Experimental trials with other metals or metalloids have not yet been conducted. The preferred concentrations are in the mg/L to 10 g/L range; recovery from µg/L solutions is feasible, however it is challenging to collect sufficient sample for analysis at laboratory scale, whereas recovery from more concentrated solutions on one hand leads to clogging of the system by the solid products formed, and on the other hand becomes less economically interesting vs other competing processes which are established industrially.
- Nature and concentration of impurities. Some impurities can have a significant impact on the GDEX process. For instance, the presence of thiourea ($\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$) can lead to the preferential formation of elemental S, when using appropriate conditions for CO_2 reduction. Although S recovery could be of interest, when the interest is on metal recovery the mixtures of the precipitated S together with elemental metals are difficult to separate. If the metal mixture is highly complex, mixed metal precipitates can be obtained, making the product generated less valuable than when the composition allows for selective recovery.
- Nature and partial pressure of gases employed. The use of O_2 (in air) leads to the formation of hydroxides and oxides, wherein valuable mixed metal oxides are possible. Conversely, the use of CO_2 leads to the formation of elemental metals for a selected group of metals like the PGMs and Cu.
- Applied cathode potential. This parameter will influence which gas can be electrochemically reduced at the gas-diffusion cathode. It will also influence the development of unwanted side reactions, like H_2 evolution, which decrease the efficiency of the process.
- Nature of the supporting electrolyte. Model GDEX experiments are typically conducted using NaCl or Na_2SO_4 as supporting electrolytes. Although these are also common supporting electrolytes in geothermal brines, their concentration and nature of the metal ions present can lead to reactions where these are incorporated. For instance, instead of metal hydroxides, metal hydroxychlorides could be formed. Some of these can also be valuable, although they are more difficult to assess. Otherwise, supporting electrolytes rich in chlorides can lead to Cl_2 evolution at the anode, for which scrubbing procedures would be necessary at larger scale, if alternative reactions cannot be implemented.
- Applied charge. The applied charge has a direct influence on the resulting pH and hence the selectivity of the metals removed and products formed. It is possible to operate the GDEX process in batch mode

wherein the pH will evolve transiently during operation, or in continuous mode wherein a fixed pH can be targeted. The applied charge will also determine the extent of removal of a certain metal.

- Temperature. The temperature in the range of 25°C to 50°C investigated during the project did not seem to have a significant influence on the GDEx recovery process. Nevertheless, it does have a significant influence on the nature of the products formed. Therefore, the choice of an operational temperature will depend on the valorisation opportunities of the recovered metals.

Feed specifications

At laboratory scale, the minimum amount to successfully operate the GDEx process ranges from 125 mL to 250 mL, in view of providing a sufficient amount of products recovered for further analysis. During the CHPM project an up-scaled reactor was also tested, using 400 L of brine. Thus, at present it is possible to process feeds with volumes from 125 mL to 1 m³ without troubles. Preferred streams should contain a few metals to be valorised, in the range of 100 mg/L to 5 g/L. Ideally, the geothermal brines provided are slightly acidic, as this generally favours the stability of metal ions as opposed to metal precipitates.

Product expectations

The GDEx process typically recovers >80% of the total metal content, in different processing stages. For some metals the recovery can be as high as >99%. The products are typically recovered in the form of (nano) particles, which are often agglomerated. In many cases it is possible to have a fine control of the product specifications (composition, particle size, crystallite size, morphology, oxidation state), as long as the stream has a stable composition at the input of the GDEx reactor. The products are stable in the solid form. Dispersions can be otherwise obtained, yet steps towards the stability of these dispersions are still needed. Variations in product quality are not expected under the same conditions of processing. However, slight changes in morphology and size can arise from changing to a larger processing scale.

Process considerations

The GDEx process alone has been described above. However, there are upstream and downstream steps that also need to be considered and likely some of them to be modified in the future, as per the optimized and larger scale implementation of the process.

No treatment is necessary to the geothermal brine at the input of the GDEx process as long as there are no large particles present. If that is the case, they need to be separated, e.g. via filtration. The anolyte employed can be also the same geothermal brine or another aqueous feedstock. The selected gas (O₂, CO₂, air) will depend on the type of products aimed for recovery. After the GDEx processing, the outflow consists of: (1) a liquid (aqueous) stream that contains dispersed nanoparticles at the exit of the cathodic compartment, (2) an exhaust anolyte at the exit of the anodic compartment, (3) exhaust gases from the whole electrochemical system. The aqueous streams to be discarded can be eventually mixed to achieve pH corrections if necessary. The liquid stream containing the dispersed nanoparticles requires to be subject to sedimentation, centrifugation or other suitable beneficiation methods to separate the (nano) particles from the residual brine (e.g. considered as a wastewater for recovery purposes, but for the overall geothermal cycle this is the exhaust brine that will follow treatment by salinity gradient power through reverse electrodialysis (SGP-RE)). The (nano) particle products can be collected as a dispersion, wet pellet or dry pellet, depending on the application or market of interest.

Figure 7. Flow diagrams of the GDEx technology and peripheral processing units for geothermal brines.

3.5 Salinity gradient power through reverse electrodialysis (SGP-RE)

The energy stored as the salinity difference between two sources exhibiting different salinities is another large-scale renewable energy source that can be exploited. Examples of saline sources can be seawater, reverse osmosis brines, saline groundwater, saline industrial effluents, salt ponds, etc. Extraction of salinity gradient energy efficiently still remains a challenge. With the development of membrane science and technology, membrane-based techniques for energy extraction from saline sources, such as pressure-retarded osmosis and reverse electro-dialysis, have made big leaps in recent years.

Reverse ElectroDialysis (RED) uses a similar process design as in electrodialysis (ED). The only difference is in the operation of the process, instead of feeding the same solution in all the compartments, in a RED unit two solutions with different concentrations are fed alternatively in the compartments. A high concentration and a low concentration solutions are needed to make this electrochemical reactor to work. The membrane stack is made of cell pairs consisting of one cation exchange membrane (CEM), one high-concentration channel (HIGH), one anion exchange membrane (AEM) and one low-concentration channel (LOW) each (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Schematic drawing of reverse electrodialysis.

The concentration gradients across the membranes cause the ions to move in opposite directions, since Na^+ can pass only through CEM and Cl^- only through AEM. Due to the transport of ions a potential difference is generated across the membranes and within a cell pair. Adding the contribution of many cell pairs, it is possible to have a significant potential between the 'end-electrodes'. This potential difference can then trigger a redox reaction. The electrolyte rinsing solution (ERS) plays a fundamental role in the operation of the process since it converts the ionic current into an electronic one. This is enabled by the redox couple present in the ERS solution and which is recirculated continuously between anode and cathode. Connecting the anode and cathode with an external load will enable an electrical current to flow. Two DSA (Dimensionally Stable Anodes) are typically used as electrodes. They are inert electrodes and their role is to catalyse the reaction of the redox species.

4 Methodology

As shown in Figure 1 the overall CHPM system is composed of the following 7 components:

- 1) Underground heat exchanger
- 2) Production wells
- 3) Electrolytic metal recovery
- 4) Geothermal binary power plant, eventually including heat delivery technology
- 5) Gas diffusion electro-precipitation
- 6) Salt gradient power generation
- 7) Injection wells

A model framework has been created based on component level models which enables linking downstream and upstream geothermal engineering subsystems. The different system components are integrated into a single system by a mathematical model. This model has been used to estimate possible metal extraction as well as electricity and heat production for selected scenarios. Sensitivity analysis have also been performed. The focus has been on the above ground components, i.e. the electrolytic metal recovery, geothermal binary power plant, gas diffusion electro-precipitation, and salt gradient power generation components. The underground heat exchanger component gives the original parameter list for the calculations and it is assumed that the production well and injection well components have no effect on the results. More detailed description of the underground components was too difficult to achieve within this current project but could be considered in future CHPM projects.

A brief overview of the approach is given below:

- The main task is to develop a mathematical model of the overall system.
- The overall model is made up of elements or sub-models describing the behaviour of each component (component models).
- Each component has an input from the previous component in the chain and an output that will feed the following component.
- The overall simulation model is used to study different scenarios and perform sensitivity analysis.
- The most important design parameters, for the current state of knowledge, have been identified.
- Mathematical description of what happens within the different components in the system has been acquired.

Sub-models describe the behaviour of each component and these are combined in one overall mathematical model. Each component has an input from the previous component in the chain and an output to the following component as shown schematically in Figure 9. Data and mathematical description has been collected for each component so that a probabilistic model can be constructed in the python programming language using the selected approach.

Figure 9. Schematic presentation of a component model.

The type and scope of the mathematical model is being developed at ISOR with inputs from other partners. The approach in the overall model is to consider each component as a “black box” into which a list of parameters is fed and out comes a new list where the parameters have been altered according to the inner workings of each component. Also, from the input parameters the energy input or output of each component is calculated.

The key parameters for the CHPM technology and the overall system dynamics were identified and reported in deliverable D4.2 (Report on overall system dynamics). Based on this the following set of parameters were proposed at an early stage of the project:

Temperature:	T	[°C]
Pressure:	P	[bar]
Acidity/basicity:	Ph	[-]
Redox condition:	Rd	[eH]
Oxygen fugacity:	fO ₂	[bar]
Carbon dioxide:	CO ₂	[bar]
Conductivity:	si	[S/m]
Flow rate:	q	[L/s]
Salinity:	S	[g/L]
Oxidizing compounds:	O _x	[mg/L]
Concentrated suspended solids:	C _{ss}	[mg/L]

After receiving data and mathematical models from the partners responsible for each component, this list was reduced. The final version of the model uses the following list of parameters:

Temperature:	T	[°C]
Pressure:	P	[bar]
Acidity/basicity:	Ph	[-]
Flow rate:	q	[L/s]
Salinity:	S	[g/L]
Concentrated suspended solids:	C _{ss}	[mg/L]

The C_{ss} parameters contain the amount of different metals in the brine. The metal content varies greatly between geothermal areas and even within each geothermal area. The extent of this variability can clearly be seen in Figure 10. The data is taken from the USGS open file database for geothermal brines (Neupane et al., 2017) which contains large variety of brine samples from the western part the US and from 6 samples from wells RN-12, RN-19, and RN-21 in the Reykjanes geothermal area in southwest Iceland, sampled in 2007 and 2014 (Hardardóttir et al., 2009; Hannington et. al., 2016). For the US samples we constrict ourselves to samples that had temperatures higher that 100°C when sampled, this adds up to 191 samples. In Figure 10 we see that across geothermal sites in the US the concentration of many metals in brines can vary more than four orders of magnitude. Interestingly, the variation of metal concentration can be over one order of magnitude within in a single geothermal site, as can be seen for that Reykjanes samples. This can result in large uncertainties in the input parameters for the system model.

Figure 10. Log scale concentration for various metals in brine samples from the Western part of the US (red and orange) and from the Reykjanes geothermal area in Iceland (blue). The US samples are brine samples from the USGS open file database for geothermal brines which are over 100°C. The right axis denotes the number of US samples that contained the metals shown on the left axis. For the US samples red denotes concentrations within in the 25% to 75% percentile range and orange outside.

Furthermore, most of the technical components are still in active development. Detailed knowledge on the interplay of various parameters within most of the components is therefore missing. Due to this uncertainty in the component models along with uncertainties of input parameters, the model approach in consideration is a probabilistic Monte Carlo model. In a Monte Carlo model each parameter is given a probability distribution according to the certainty of its value. The model is then run multiple times using randomly selected set of parameters for each run. In the end a probability distribution for energy use and metal extraction is created.

As a simple example, in Figure 11 the input and output probability distribution for the current version of the geothermal binary plant component are shown. Here the inlet temperature is taken to be in the range from 70°C to 150°C with a triangular probability distribution with the mode at 120°C. The output distribution in Figure 11 (b) shows the range of power to be expected from the input temperature distribution in Figure 11 (a).

Figure 11. (a) Input probability distribution for temperature for the binary power plant component. (b) Output probability distribution for power production for the binary power plant component.

The models for the Gas diffusion electro-precipitation component and the Electrolytic metal recovery component involve uncertainty within the component models. For example, the amount of energy per kg of extracted metal as a function of Mg concentrations and salinity for the Gas diffusion electro-precipitation component is currently based on the blue data points in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Relation between energy use of the Gas diffusion electro-precipitation component as a function of (a) Mg concentration and (b) salinity.

The relation for energy use as a function of Mg concentrations and salinity is deduced from a generalized linear regression analysis, shown in orange in Figure 12. The regression analysis gives uncertainty ranges that can be used in the Monte Carlo modelling. In Figure 12 the standard error that results from the generalized linear regression analysis is calculated by running the model 1000 times for each measured brine data point.

The selected model approach for the CHPM plant allows us to quantitatively evaluate the uncertainty of our current state of knowledges.

4.1 Component models

4.1.1 Component model for electrolytic metal recovery

An analytical model was created for electrolytic metal recovery from geothermal brines. The model is based on Faraday’s laws assuming a concentration depended recovery rate and energetic efficiency. The electric power consumption is calculated from the amount of metal recovered and the energetic efficiency. The model is valid for noble metals, i.e., metals that have a standard reduction potential equal or above +0.34 V (for Cu).

The model was validated against the experimental data obtained in WP3. The experimental data reveals recoveries of 80 – 90%. The recovery tends to correlate with the initial concentration: high initial concentrations reveals slightly lower recovery (Table 2). It should be noted that batch experiments were used to evaluate metal recovery from brines. In a CHPM plant, flow through technologies will be used. In this case, recovery will depend on the contact time between the brine and the electrodes. Hence, it can be expected that the recovery will be a function of flow rate with lower flow rates resulting in higher recoveries.

The energy consumption depends on the initial concentration of ions. For high initial concentrations, the energy consumption approaches the theoretical value calculated by Faraday’s laws. The electrical efficiency decreases with decreasing initial concentration.

Table 2. Recovery of Cu and energy consumption at 150°C, 50 bar and a potential of 500 mV vs Pt as a function of initial concentration (C_{in}).

C _{in} (ppm)	C _{end} (ppm)	Recovery	E (kWh/kg)
690	131	81.0%	0.4
345	40	88.4%	1.1
165	22.5	86.4%	2.1

The component model calculates the mass of metal recovery from the flow rate and the initial concentration:

$$m = Q \times C_{in} \times R \tag{1}$$

With Q the brine flow rate in L/s, C_{in} the initial metal concentration in g/l and R the recovery rate. R is calculated by the following exponential function that fitted to the experimental data:

$$R = 1 - e^{(-80/Q)} \tag{2}$$

The corresponding energy consumption is derived from Faraday’s laws:

$$I = m \times F_c \times \left| \frac{z \times e_{elec}}{mm} \right| \quad (3)$$

With F_c Faraday's constant (96485 C/mol), z the valency of the metallic ion, mm the molar mass (g/mol) and e_{elec} the electrical efficiency. e_{elec} is calculated by the following exponential function that fitted to the experimental data:

$$e_{elec} = 0.15 \times e^{2.7 \times C_{in}} \quad (4)$$

Figure 13 shows the final concentration of metals and energy consumption of the component as a function of the initial metal concentration.

Figure 13. Component model output for the final concentration (dashed red lines show 95% confidence interval) and results of the experiments at 150°C, 50 bar, at a potential of 500 mV vs Pt (quasi reversible electrode) to reduce Cu from the brine (blue dots).

4.1.2 Component model for combined heat and power production

The component model for combined heat and power production is based on the work of Walraven et al. (2015a & b) and Van Erdeweghe et al. (2017 & 2019). Van Erdeweghe (2017) showed that for the combination of a binary unit with high temperature district heating connected to a low temperature geothermal source, the HB4 configuration proposed by Habka & Ajib (2014) in most cases has the highest efficiency. In case of low flow rates (< 10 kg/s) and low source temperature (< 120°C), a simple parallel configuration can be more efficient. For district heating with a low supply temperature (lower than the outlet temperature of the binary cycle), a series configuration in most cases is preferable.

The component model makes it possible to select a specific configuration to combine heat and electricity production from a single source. For simplicity of the calculation, a parallel configuration is assumed for high temperature heat supply and a series configuration for low temperature heat supply. The difference between high and low temperature heat supply is made based on the estimated outlet temperature of the binary cycle.

In case of a series configuration, the brine mass flow over the evaporator of the binary system is equal to the mass flow rate of the geothermal source. In case of a parallel configuration, the mass flow rate over the binary cycle is equal to:

$$\dot{m}_{orc} = \dot{m}_b - \dot{m}_{DH} \quad (5)$$

Where \dot{m}_b is the mass flow rate from the production well(s) and \dot{m}_{DH} is the mass flow rate over the heat exchanger of the district heating system. The \dot{m}_{DH} is calculated based on the heat demand for district heating:

$$\dot{m}_{DH} = \frac{P_{DH}}{c_{p_b} \times (T_{b,i} - T_{b,hto} - T_{pitch})} \quad (6)$$

With P_{DH} the heat demand for the high temperature district heating system/heating application covered by geothermal [kW], c_{p_b} the specific heat capacity of the brine [J/(kg °C)], $T_{b,hto}$ the output temperature of the high temperature branch of the geothermal CHP installation [°C] and T_{pitch} the pinch temperature of the high temperature/parallel heat exchanger [°C]. $T_{b,hto}$ is calculated as the mixing temperature of the brine derived from the output of the binary cycle and from the high temperature/parallel heat exchanger for high temperature heat supply.

Typically, heat demand fluctuates on a daily, weekly, monthly and yearly basis. In the case of geothermal district heating or other applications with a highly variable heat demand, it is not cost-effective to design the geothermal heat supply to match peak demand. Good performance of a combined heat and power geothermal system is usually reached when 60 – 70% of the heat demand is covered by the geothermal source and the remaining heat demand is supplied by peak boilers. The component model by default uses a cut-off of 60% of the maximal demand of a connected high-temperature heating application (assumed to be district heating).

To calculate P_{DH} the annual heat demand is split in an hourly demand using standard demand curves for specific applications. All models were run using a demand curve for district heating (Figure 14). The hourly demand is then compared to the maximal geothermal power that can be supplied by the well(s). In case the demand is higher than the available geothermal heating capacity, the energy delivered is set to the capacity of the well(s). In case the demand is lower than the available capacity, the energy delivered is set to the demand. By default, a 60% cut-off is used for high temperature heating. The cut-off tops off the high hourly demands (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Demand profile for a district heating system with an annual heat consumption of 10,000 MWh.

The outlet temperature of the binary cycle depends on the thermal properties of the brine, the working fluid used in the binary cycle, the cooling system and the ambient conditions. The outlet temperature is calculated using a correlation against the results of a thermodynamic optimisation model for a single-pressure organic Rankine system using isobutane as working fluid. The input temperature ranges from of 100 to 150°C and the condenser input temperature varies between 0 and 30°C (Walraven et al., 2013). A different correlation is used for air cooled and water-cooled systems.

In addition, the minimal outlet temperature is also defined by the scaling properties of the geothermal brine. This factor is not considered by the current model.

The net power output of the CHP module is calculated using the following equation:

$$kW_e^{net} = \frac{cp_b \times (T_{b,i} - T_{b,orco}) \times \dot{m}_{orc} \times \gamma_{en}^{cycle}}{1000 \times 100} \quad (7)$$

With $T_{b,i}$ the production temperature of the geothermal well(s) [°C], $T_{b,orco}$ the brine outlet temperature of the binary installation [°C], the \dot{m}_{orc} the mass flow rate over the binary system [kg/s] and γ_{en}^{cycle} the net energy efficiency of the cycle.

cp_b is calculated from the brine temperature and salinity using the formula given by Batzle & Wang (1992).

The net efficiency and brine outlet temperature of the binary system are calculated based on correlations of the results from a thermodynamic optimisation of binary cycles (Walraven et al., 2013). Distinction is made between air cooled and water-cooled systems.

For air cooled systems, the net efficiency is calculated using the following correlation:

$$\gamma_{en}^{cycle} = (-5.182 \times 10^{-4} \times T_{b,i}^2 + 0.2307 \times T_{b,i} - 10.71) \times c_{T_0} \quad (8)$$

With c_{T_0} a term to correct for changes in the dead-state temperature:

$$c_{T_0} = \frac{(T_{b,i} - T_0) \times (556.6 + T_{b,i})}{(546.3 + T_{b,i} + T_0)} \quad (9)$$

The brine outlet temperature is calculated using the following correlation:

$$T_{b,orco} = 0.0317 \times T_{b,i} + 60.9 \quad (10)$$

For water cooled system, the following correlations are used:

$$\gamma_{en}^{cycle} = (8.434 \times 10^{-2} \times T_{b,i} - 0.4457) \times c_{T_0} \quad (11)$$

$$T_{b,orco} = 0.1211 \times T_{b,i} + 44.138 \quad (12)$$

4.1.3 Component model for the gas diffusion electro-crystallisation metal extraction (GDEx)

The calibration of the model for the gas-diffusion electrocrystallization component (GDEx) is based on data presented in deliverable D3.2 (Report on performance, mass and energy balances and design criteria for gas-diffusion electroprecipitation and electrocrystallization). In the report the energy usage and ratios of recovered metals from brine is measured for different values of Mg and Ca concentrations, salinity (S), working electrode potential (Ewe), temperature (T), and pH. Most of these samples were simulated in the lab. The simulated samples can be divided into two groups, (1) simulated samples that are based on real brine samples from England, Belgium, and Iceland (Hardardóttir et al., 2009) and (2) simulated samples where emphasis was

put on studying Li and Al recovery for different parameters and brine compositions. The latter group makes up the bulk of the lab simulated samples. Also, a few samples were composed of real brine from Romania. The values of measured recovery ratio of Li and Al metals, energy used per kg of recovered metal, values of Mg and Ca concentration, salinity, working electrode potential, temperature, and pH for each sample can be found in Appendix A, Table 27). Measured recovery ratios for other metals found in the Romanian brine are in Appendix A, Table 28).

The energy input used per kg of recovered metals and ratios of metal recovery are modelled via linear regression analysis using the StatsModel package in Python (Seabold et al, 2010). For the model of energy per kg of recovered metals the logarithm is taken of the energy values. This is done to ensure that the model gives positive energy results and catches any power relations that connect the energy values to the input parameters. The resulting model is described by the following equation:

$$E_{in} = \exp(A + B \cdot Mg + C \cdot Ca + D \cdot Ph + E \cdot S + F \cdot T + G \cdot Ewe), \quad (13)$$

where A, B, C, D, E, F, and G are the model parameters that are estimated from the regression analysis. The regression analysis was performed on the simulated brine samples that were used to study Al and Li extraction (sample 7 to sample 75 in Appendix A, Table 27) which we will call the lab samples. The reason for restricting the regression to the lab samples is that they compose the largest share of the samples. Furthermore, the other sample types, the simulated Iceland samples (samples 1 and 2), the simulated Belgium samples (samples 3 and 4), the simulated England samples (samples 5 and 6), and the real Romanian brine samples (samples 76 to 79) can be used to test the robustness of the model. The estimates of these values, made by the regression analysis, along with the standard deviations of the values can be seen in Table 3.

Two types of models were constructed: one where the model parameters are assigned the values produced from the linear regression analysis and another where model parameters are randomly assigned from normal distributions constructed from the values and standard deviations produced by the linear regression analysis.

Table 3. Model parameters for the energy input per kg of extracted metal found in Equation 13 according to the linear regression analysis.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
	[-]	[(mg/L) ⁻¹]	[(mg/L) ⁻¹]	[-]	[(g/L) ⁻¹]	[°C ⁻¹]	[V ⁻¹]
Value	1.35	1.64 × 10 ⁻³	-0.82 × 10 ⁻⁵	7.56 × 10 ⁻²	4.99 × 10 ⁻³	0.12 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.71
Std.	0.35	0.18 × 10 ⁻³	1.57 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.24 × 10 ⁻²	2.22 × 10 ⁻³	6.56 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.41

In Figure 15 the results of the model for energy input per kg of recovered metals is compared to measured values. The colour of the measured points and background indicates the type of the sample. The dark blue points are the model results where the model parameters are assigned the values produced by the regression analysis. The difference between the measured values and the model values are shown as red bars around the horizontal zero line. The mean model error is 0.7 kWh/kg, but it ranges from -18.3 kWh/kg to 31.6 kWh/kg. Around the model points are the ranges that the model with the random model parameters produced after 1000 runs. The blue error bars show the range that 68% of these model runs fell within and the grey lines show the range that 95% fell within. A more detailed picture of these distributions can be seen in Appendix A, Figure 53.

As seen in Figure 15 the model seems to follow the simulated lab samples reasonably well but produces large uncertainties for higher values of energy inputs. The model also roughly captures the energy input of the simulated samples that represent brine from England, Iceland, and Belgium, but the uncertainty ranges do not

always cover the measured values. The worst comparison seems to be for the real Romanian brines, where the model seems to consistently overestimates the energy input required. This shows the need to recalibrate the model for real world brines when measurements will be available.

It is important to note that the flow rate of the experiments that are used to calibrate the model was 40 ml/min or around 6.6×10^{-4} L/s. The flow that a standard geothermal power plant consumes is on the order of 100 L/s or nearly five orders of magnitude larger. Therefore, in the final system model the model output based on current experimental results is extrapolated linearly by a factor on the order of magnitude of 10^5 .

When modelling the metal recovery ratio, we insist that the model returns results in the range from 0 to 1. To achieve this, we perform a logistic regression. This is done by applying a logit transform:

$$\text{logit}(x) = \log\left(\frac{x}{1-x}\right) \tag{14}$$

on the metal recovery ratios followed by a linear regression analysis. After the linear regression analysis, we need to transform our model back with an inverse with the following transform:

$$S(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \tag{15}$$

commonly known as the sigmoid function. Using this approach, the resulting model for the Al and Li metal recovery ratios are the following:

$$M_{Al-out} = \frac{1.0}{1.0 + \exp(-[A + B \cdot Mg + C \cdot Ca + D \cdot Ph + E \cdot S + F \cdot T + G \cdot Ewe])} \tag{16}$$

and

$$M_{Li-out} = \frac{0.4}{1.0 + \exp(-[A + B \cdot Mg + C \cdot Ca + D \cdot Ph + E \cdot S + F \cdot T + G \cdot Ewe])} \tag{17}$$

Here the model parameters A, B, C, D, E, F, and G are estimated from the linear regression analysis. The values of the model parameters and their standard deviation can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found**. Here again we make two types of models one where we use the values of the model parameters directly and one where we use random values from normal distributions constructed from the values and standard deviations.

Table 4. Regression parameters for the ratios of extracted Al and Li found in Equation 16 and Equation 17, respectively.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
	[-]	[(mg/L) ⁻¹]	[(mg/L) ⁻¹]	[-]	[(g/L) ⁻¹]	[°C ⁻¹]	[V ⁻¹]
AL Value	9.24	7.29×10^{-4}	2.38×10^{-5}	-6.10×10^{-1}	-1.02×10^{-2}	0.76×10^{-2}	-0.85
AL Std.	1.17	5.48×10^{-4}	4.98×10^{-5}	0.93×10^{-1}	0.65×10^{-2}	2.51×10^{-2}	1.19
Li Value	-2.17	-3.85×10^{-4}	1.29×10^{-4}	1.05×10^{-1}	1.68×10^{-2}	0.06×10^{-2}	2.14×10^{-1}
Li Std.	0.52	0.24×10^{-4}	0.22×10^{-4}	0.42×10^{-1}	0.29×10^{-2}	1.12×10^{-2}	5.29×10^{-1}

Figure 15. Comparison of the calibrated model for the energy input per extracted metal mass (Equation 13) and measured values.

The comparison between values calculated with the regression model and measured values of the Al recovery ratio for each sample can be seen in Figure 16. We see there that the model values roughly follow the measured values for most samples, the biggest discrepancies are for sample 15 and sample 75. Also indicated on the figure are the 68% and 95% uncertainty ranges calculated after 1000 runs of the random parameter model. These distributions can also be seen in Appendix B, Figure 53. The model error or the difference between the (non-random) model values and measured values are shown as red bars. The mean model error is -0.029 but ranges from -0.098 to 0.80.

Figure 16. Comparison of the calibrated model for the ratio of extracted Al and measured values.

All the measured data points for the Li ratios lie in the range of 0 to 0.4. When fitting the model to the measured data the best results were achieved when the regression was forced to be in the range of 0 to 0.4 by using a scaled sigmoid transform. Note that we also scaled the standard deviation of the model parameters for the lithium model by 0.4. This is done to avoid too much binary behaviour of the probability distribution. The comparison between calculated values and measured values of Li recovery ratios can be seen in Figure 17. The model result appears to crudely follow the measured values except for a few samples, 42, 56, 58, and 61, where measured values fall outside the uncertainty range produced by the model. Again, a more detailed picture of the distributions can be found in Appendix B, Figure 53. The mean model error for the Li model is -0.011 but ranges from -0.26 to 0.16. Note that Figure 16 and Figure 17 only include samples which contained Li or Al.

Figure 17. Comparison of the calibrated model for the ratio of extracted Li and measured values.

Data for ratios of other recovered metals, Sr, Mn, Ba, As, Zn, Rb, Ni, and Ba, are also presented in deliverable D3.2. (Report on performance, mass and energy balances and design criteria for gas-diffusion electroprecipitation and electrocrystallization). An effort was made to fit a logistic regression model to the data but as this part of the data is rather scarce (only 2 or 4 data points per metal), finding a suitable regression model proved to be difficult. Due to the difficulty of producing a robust model based on a regression analysis, a simpler approach was adopted. For each metal a uniform distribution was created. The bounds of these distributions are one standard deviation from the mean value of the metal extraction ratios. The comparison of the model to measured values can be found in Figure 18. The samples presented are samples 76 to 79, or the Romanian samples. The points and background are coloured according to the metals. For Sr, Ba, As, and Zn four measurements for metal recovery where available but only two for Mn, Rb, and Ni. The bars for the model errors are calculated by the difference between the mean values and measured values.

Figure 18. Comparison of the calibrated model for the ratio of extracted (a) Sr, (b) Mn, (c) Ba, (d) As, (e) Zn, (f) Rb, and (g) Ni and measured values.

4.1.4 Component model for salinity gradient power (SGP-RE)

The SGP-RE process is modelled, using an approach described in Tedesco et al., 2012, on the modelling of the reverse electrodialysis process with seawater and concentrated brines, combined with the 2-D approach described in Tedesco et al. 2014.

The model uses the basic Nernst equation to solve the concentration profiles across the ion-exchange membranes of the dilute and concentrate compartments, resp. LOW and HIGH. The Nernst equation determines the membrane potential as a function of the concentration difference between dilute and concentrate. Applied to a cell pair (one AEM, one CEM, one dilute compartment, one concentrate compartment) the cell potential can be expressed as the sum of the two Nernst potentials across the respective membranes:

$$E_{\text{cell}} = \alpha_{\text{CEM}} \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{\gamma_b^{\text{Na}}(x)C_b(x)}{\gamma_s^{\text{Na}}(x)C_s(x)} + \alpha_{\text{AEM}} \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{\gamma_b^{\text{Cl}}(x)C_b(x)}{\gamma_s^{\text{Cl}}(x)C_s(x)} \quad (18)$$

With subscripts ‘b’ referring to the HIGH and subscripts ‘s’ referring to the LOW. The concentration of the salt in the brine and surface water is mentioned (C_b and C_s) since equimolar amounts of Na and Cl will be present in the same solution. Concentrations and activity coefficients are expressed as function of the position along the path length of the stack ($C_b(x)$). Furthermore, the cell potential of a half-cell will be ‘tuned’ by adding tuning parameters to Equation 18. The cell pair resistance consists of the resistance of the two membranes and the resistance of both HIGH and LOW compartments. Expressed as function of the position x along the pathlength axis this becomes:

$$R_{\text{cell}}(x) = R_b(x) + R_s(x) + R_{\text{CEM}} + R_{\text{AEM}} \quad (19)$$

In Figure 19 a schematic is given of a SGP-RE cell consisting of one CEM and one AEM. The cell has a path length L , width b and thickness h_b . The HIGH and LOW liquids enter the compartments from the top. As the fluid is flowing downwards, the concentration will change through diffusion of the ions through the respective membranes. For the infinitesimal volume that is shown at position x , the mass balances for both compartments are described as:

$$\frac{dC_s(x)}{dx} = \frac{b}{Q_s} J_{\text{tot}}(x) \quad (20a)$$

$$\frac{dC_b(x)}{dx} = -\frac{b}{Q_b} J_{\text{tot}}(x) \quad (20b)$$

This model for a single cell pair can be used to develop a higher scale model for a stack, consisting of n cell pairs, combining Equation 18 and Equation 19 to determine the stack potential and internal resistance, hence the power output in combination with a given external load.

Figure 19. Simulating model for one cell pair in a stack with n cell pairs.

Python was used to convert the above model and equations to the appropriate code. The model is valid for pure NaCl solutions but can be post-calibrated for the presence of (small quantities of) multivalent ions.

The inputs for the simulation are:

- The concentration of the high and low salinity sources in mol/m³
- The flow rate of the high and low feed streams in m³/s
- The temperature (T): it is assumed both streams have the same temperature, which is a valid assumption if one considers the possibility of heat recovery from the spent brine to the incoming low salinity source (e.g. surface water).
- The salt efficiency (SE) or desired desalination: a fraction of the salinity of the brine which is transferred to the low salinity stream. E.g.: a 2M brine with 40% SE would imply that the program will simulate a number of stacks until the last stack reaches a brine outlet concentration of 1.2M.

The global stack parameters and constants that are used in the program:

- l: length of stack (m): can be chosen arbitrarily, based on expert judgement.
- b: width of stack (m): can be chosen arbitrarily, based on expert judgement.
- R= 8.31 (J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹).
- F= 96485 (As Eq-1).
- Raem = AEM resistance (ohm.m²) - (FAS20: 0.5 Ohm.cm²): value taken from membrane specs.
- Rcem = CEM resistance (ohm.m²) - (FKS20: 1.7 Ohm.cm²): value taken from membrane specs.
- tk = transport number CEM (FKS20 99%PS --> (0.99+1)/2=0.995=tk).
- ta = transport number AEM (FAS20 96%PS --> (0.96+1)/2=0.98).
- v_b brine flow velocity (m s⁻¹): can be chosen arbitrarily, based on expert judgement.
- f = obstruction factor (1/spacer shadow): estimated or based on projected contact area (spacer vs membrane).

Below is an example given of calculation of the power output when applying SGP-RE to brine in combination with surface water. Both streams are assumed to contain pure NaCl. The input parameters for the simulation were:

- Cb_in: 2000mM
- Qb_in: 100m³/h
- Cr_in: 200mM
- Qr_in: 100m³/h
- T: 323K (50°C)
- SE: 22% (desired desalination)

The global stack parameters and constants that are used in the program:

- | | |
|-----------------------------|---|
| • l: length of stack [m]: | 1m |
| • b: width of stack [m]: | 1m |
| • R= | 8.31 [J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹] |
| • F= | 96485 [As Eq-1] |
| • Raem = | FAS20: 0,5 Ohm.cm |
| • Rcem = | FKS20: 1,7 Ohm.cm |
| • tk = transport number CEM | 0.995 |
| • ta = transport number AEM | 0.98 |
| • v_b brine flow velocity | 1 m s ⁻¹ |
| • f = obstruction factor | 1/0.8 |

The main results of the simulation are shown in Table 5. In total three stacks were calculated according to the specification given above (length and width, flow velocity). The final desalination degree is 21.9%, just greater than the requested 20%. From the table it is already clear that the power output of the three stack is declining from 5.3 W/m³ in the first stack, over 2.9 W/m² in the second stack, over 1.7 W/m² in the third stack.

Table 5. Overview of the simulation results (2M vs 0.02M NaCl, 50°C, 100m³/h).

stack_nr		1	2	3
U_mean	V	649	448	333
P_W_m2	W/m ²	5.3	2.9	1.7
P_tot	W	36812	19796	11574
P_pump_tot	W	304	304	304
P_net	W	36508	19492	11270
R_mean	Ohm	7.07	6.79	6.69
I_mean	A	57	44	35
OCV_mean	V	1051	748	566
N		13889	13889	13889
S	m ²	6944	6944	6944
Ru	Ohm	11.43	10.15	9.60
h_b	m	0.0002	0.0002	0.0002
Qb_in	m ³ /s	0.027778	0.027778	0.027778
Cb_in	mol/m ³	2000	1819	1675
Qr_in	m ³ /s	0.027778	0.027778	0.027778
Cr_in	mol/m ³	200	381	525
T	K	323	323	323
SE		0.091	0.162	0.219

The program also plots the power curves in the three stacks, this is shown in Figure 20. The same trend is visible here: a decline in maximum power output density [W/m²]. Also, it is clear that the voltage at maximum output drops significantly from stack 1 to stack 3. Next to these two forms of output, a table with the complete concentration profile over the stack length is given for each stack.

Figure 20. Powerplot simulation results (2M vs 0,02M NaCl, 50°C, 100m³/h).

4.2 System modelling tools

The system model is programmed in the Python programming language, available at <http://www.python.org>. The Monte Carlo simulation consists of a loop that runs a series of functions, C3, C4, C5, and C6, that model each of the above ground components: the electrolysis component, the geothermal power plant component, the gas diffusion electrolysis and electrocrystallization component, and the salt gradient power plant component, respectively. A schematic of the program structure can be seen in Figure 21. Each of the functions take in the parameter list in a form of a python dictionary p where the keys of the dictionary identify the parameters. All functions return an appropriately altered version of the parameter list and how much energy E was either consumed or produced in MW_e. The change in the parameter list is due to changes in the brine when it goes through the component. This can be for example change in the temperature of the brine when it goes through the geothermal power plant component or removal of metal from the brine in the gas diffusion electrolysis component. The functions that model the components that recover metal from the brine, C3 and C5, representing the electrolysis component and gas diffusion electrolysis component respectively, also return a python dictionary M that contains the values for the recovered amount in mg/L for each metal. The C4 function, representing the power plant component, also returns the amount H of heat produced for direct use in MW_{th}. After each iteration the output variables E_3 , M_3 , E_4 , H_4 , E_5 , M_5 , and E_6 are stored in Pandas DataFrames, available at <https://pandas.pydata.org>, for further data analysis. The preparation of input parameters, execution of the program and postprocessing is done via Jupyter notebooks, available at <https://jupyter.org>.

Figure 21. Schematics of the Monte Carlo model.

5 Results

Data of chemical composition of brine was collected from the following geothermal sites: Reykjanes in Iceland, Landau in Germany, Balmatt in Belgium, Cornwall in England, and the Pannonian Basin in Romania. From the collected data, probability distributions of input parameters were constructed and Monte-Carlo runs with 10,000 random realizations of input parameters performed for each site. The results from these runs are presented in this chapter. For each run we assume full scale utilization of the components. That is, the entire flow rate is used in the metal extraction and power generation. Therefore, these results should be considered to be the estimate of the maximum performance achievable according to our current knowledge of the CHPM system. Note also that the model for the electrolytic metal reduction is restricted to extracting noble metals that are applicable for Faraday's law of electrolysis. The power usages predicted by the gas diffusion is per kg of extracted metals. Therefore, so not to underestimate the power usage, we assume possible metal extraction for all metals in the gas diffusion component. For metals where we do not have measured extraction ratios, we assume uniform probability of extraction ratio from 0% to 100%, which is the quantification of maximum uncertainty.

Table 6 gives a summary of the model results for the five scenarios mentioned above. The results are in the form of most likely or average values. Actually, the results of the Monte Carlo calculations performed are in the form of probability distributions and these more detailed results are presented for each scenario separately in sub-chapters 5.1 – 5.5.

Table 6. Summary of the model results for the selected scenarios.

	Reykjanes		Landau		Balmatt		Cornwall		Romania	
Q (L/s)	100		40		40		40		55	
T (°C)	150		123		121		175		140	
S (g/L)	35		103		169		10.8		10.8	
Metal extracted	mg/L	kg/h	mg/L	kg/h	mg/L	kg/h	mg/L	kg/h	mg/L	kg/h
Cu – Copper	17	6.12	0.038	0.005	0.017	0.002	0.4	0.058	0.2	0.04
As – Arsenic	0.11	0.039	9.7	1.4						
Ag – Silver	0.06	0.022								
Sb – Antimony	0.013	0.005								
Fe- Iron	40	14.4	40	5.8	300	43.2			0.7	0.14
Br – Bromine	30	10.8	100	14.4	70	10.1				
Zn – Zink	5	1.8							1.3	0.26
Sr – Strontium			230	33.1	220	31.7	13	1.9	200	40
Li – Lithium			50	7.2			6	0.86		
Ba – Barium					10	1.4			5	1
B – Boron							4	0.58		
Mn - Manganese							3.4	0.49		
Total metal extr.	92	33	430	62	600	86	27	3.9	207	41
El. generation MW _e										
Binary plant	3.6		1.3		2.2		2.3		1.6	
Salt gradient plant	0.083		0.084		0.6		0.008		0.01	
Electrolysis comp.	-0.3		-0.12		-0.00016		-0.005		-0.003	
Gas diffusion comp.	-0.3		-0.6		-3		-0.08		-6	
Net el. generation	3.1		0.7		-0.2		2.2		-4.4	
Heat generation	3		3		6.8		3.4		2.7	

5.1 Reykjanes brine scenario

Reykjanes geothermal system is located at the toe of the Reykjanes peninsula, SW Iceland. The peninsula is constructed solely of Postglacial and Late Pleistocene basaltic (tholeiitic) lavas. No felsic rocks have been found on the peninsula. Reykjanes system is a small area, 1 km away from the Atlantic Ocean which surrounds the area by three sides. Manifestations on surface are ca 1 km² and based on drillhole cuttings (35 drillholes are in the area), the first 1000 m are dominated by hyaloclastite, volcanic breccias and tuffaceous units (Tómasson and Kristmannsdóttir, 1972). At greater depths basalt flows and intrusions are more common with increasing depths (Franzson, 2004). Reykjanes is an analogous to seafloor hydrothermal systems in terms of host rock type and low water/rock alteration.

The reservoir fluid is modified seawater, enriched in SiO₂, K, Ca and depleted in Mg and SO₄ compared with seawater (Table 7). The temperatures are in the range 270-320°C at depths between 1000 and 2500 m. Downhole fluid (~1500 m depth) contains high concentrations of metals: Cu up to 17 mg/L, Fe up to 140 mg/L, Zn up to 27 mg/L, Pb up to 0.290 mg/L and Au and Ag up to 6 and 107 µg/L (Hardardóttir et al., 2019).

The distribution of the input parameters and metal concentrations can be found in Table 7. For the Reykjanes area we fix the temperature at 150°C and the flow rate at 100 L/s of the input brine. The salinity and pH value of the input brine are given uniform distributions. Histograms of 10,000 random realizations of these uniform distributions can be seen in Figure 22.

The metals extracted by the electrolytic metal extraction component (No. 3 in Figure 1) are listed in Table 8 along with the amount of metals extracted in mg/L and the metal extraction rates in g/s. The histograms showing the probability distributions of the amount of extracted metals are shown in Figure 23. Table 9 shows the amount of extracted and extraction rate of metals for the gas diffusion electrolysis component (No. 4 in Figure 1). Histograms of probability distribution of the top four extracted metals by the gas diffusion component is shown in Figure 24.

The electric power and heat power production or consumption of each component is broken down in Table 10, along with net electric power and heat power for the whole CHPM plant. The corresponding histograms for power production or consumption of each component and of the whole CHPM loop are shown in Figure 25. Note that although the input temperature is fixed the electric power output of the geothermal power plant has a very small variance due to the distribution of the input brine salinity.

Figure 22. Probability distributions for the input parameters for the Reykjanes brine: (a) salinity (b) pH. The distributions were constructed from 10,000 random realizations of the input parameters.

Table 7. Input parameters representing brine from the Reykjanes geothermal area.

Parameter			Minimum value	Most likely value	Maximum value
Temperature	t	[°C]	-	150	-
Pressure	p	[bar]		4.74	
Acidity/Basicity	pH	[-]	4.6	-	4.9
Flow rate	q	[L/s]	-	100	-
Salinity	s	[g/L]	30	-	40
Chloride	Cl	[mg/L]	17570	-	18750
Sodium	Na	[mg/L]	93000	-	9490
Calcium	Ca	[mg/L]	1750	-	1940
Potassium	K	[mg/L]	1540	-	1680
Silicon	Si	[mg/L]	290	-	331
Iron	Fe	[mg/L]	8.92	-	140
Bromine	Br	[mg/L]	61.4	-	71.9
Zink	Zn	[mg/L]	5.35	-	26.7
Copper	Cu	[mg/L]	13.7	-	17.2
Thallium	Tl	[mg/L]	11.5	-	12.6
Barium	Ba	[mg/L]	10.1	-	10.8
Magnesium	Mg	[mg/L]	2.04	-	9.89
Strontium	Sr	[mg/L]	9.12	-	9.55
Boron	B	[mg/L]	7.68	-	8.03
Lithium	Li	[mg/L]	6.4	-	6.7
Manganese	Mn	[mg/L]	2.04	-	2.95
Iodine	I	[mg/L]	0.369	-	1.12
Nickel	Ni	[mg/L]	0.146	-	0.554
Lead	Pb	[mg/L]	0.118	-	0.293
Cadmium	Cd	[mg/L]	0.056	-	0.181
Arsenic	As	[mg/L]	0.113	-	0.154
Chromium	Cr	[mg/L]	0.0115	-	0.141
Silver	Ag	[mg/L]	0.028	-	0.107
Tellerium	Te	[mg/L]	0.0193	-	0.0628
Sulphur	S	[mg/L]	0.0268	-	0.0398
Molybdenum	Mo	[mg/L]	0.0127	-	0.0335
Antimony	Sb	[mg/L]	0.0063	-	0.025
Tungsten	W	[mg/L]	0.00637	-	0.0209
Vanadium	V	[mg/L]	0.0051	-	0.014
Beryllium	Be	[mg/L]	0.0127	-	0.014
Cobalt	Co	[mg/L]	0.0127	-	0.014
Bismuth	Bi	[mg/L]	0.0127	-	0.014
Gold	Au	[mg/L]	0.00127	-	0.0128
Selenium	Se	[mg/L]	0.00178	-	0.0104
Tin	Sn	[mg/L]	0.00127	-	0.00698
Mercury	Hg	[mg/L]	0.000405	-	0.000552

Figure 23. Probability distributions of metal extractions by the electrolysis component from the Reykjanes brine for (a) Copper, (b) Arsenic, (c) Silver, (d) Antimony, and (e) Gold.

Table 8. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the electrolysis component from the Reykjanes brine for Copper, Arsenic, Silver, Antimony, and Gold.

Metal	Mean extraction per volume of brine [mg/L]	Mean metal extraction rate [g/s]
Copper Cu	13 ± 1	1.3 ± 0.1
Arsenic As	0.11 ± 0.01	0.011 ± 0.001
Silver Ag	0.06 ± 0.02	0.006 ± 0.002
Antimony Sb	0.013 ± 0.005	0.0013 ± 0.0005
Gold Au	0.006 ± 0.003	0.0006 ± 0.0003

Figure 24. The four most extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Reykjanes brine: (a) Iron, (b) Bromine, (c) Zink, and (d) Copper.

Table 9. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Reykjanes brine.

Metal		Mean extraction per volume of brine [mg/L]	Mean metal extraction rate [g/s]
Iron	Fe*	40 ± 30	4 ± 3
Bromine	Br*	30 ± 20	3 ± 2
Zink	Zn	5 ± 4	0.5 ± 0.4
Copper	Cu*	4 ± 3	0.4 ± 0.3
Barium	Ba	3 ± 2	0.3 ± 0.2
Strontium	Sr	2 ± 2	0.2 ± 0.2
Boron	B*	4 ± 2	0.4 ± 0.2
Lithium	Li	0.4 ± 0.5	0.04 ± 0.05
Manganese	Mn	1.9 ± 0.3	0.19 ± 0.03
Nickel	Ni	0.09 ± 0.08	0.009 ± 0.008
Lead	Pb*	0.05 ± 0.05	0.005 ± 0.005
Cadmium	Cd*	0.03 ± 0.03	0.003 ± 0.003
Arsenic	As*	0.02 ± 0.01	0.002 ± 0.001
Chromium	Cr*	0.04 ± 0.03	0.004 ± 0.003
Silver	Ag*	0.02 ± 0.02	0.002 ± 0.002
Molybdenum	Mo*	0.006 ± 0.006	0.0006 ± 0.0006
Antimony	Sb*	0.004 ± 0.004	0.0004 ± 0.0004
Cobalt	Co*	0.003 ± 0.003	0.0003 ± 0.0003
Gold	Au*	0.002 ± 0.002	0.0002 ± 0.0002
Selenium	Se*	0.003 ± 0.002	0.0003 ± 0.0002
Mercury	Hg*	0.00002 ± 0.00001	0.000002 ± 0.000001

*No extraction measurements available, extraction fraction is produced from a uniform distribution from 0% to 100%.

Figure 25. Resulting distributions for the Reykjanes site: (a) the power input for the electrolysis component, (b) the power output of the geothermal power plant, (c) the power input for the gas diffusion component, (d) the power output of the salt gradient power component, and (e) the net electric power balance of the whole CHPM system.

Table 10. Mean power produced or consumed by components in CHPM plant for the Reykjanes site.

Component	Mean electric power produced/consumed [MW _e]	Thermal power produced [MW _{th}]
Electrolysis component	- 0.3 ± 0.1	-
Geothermal power plant	3.640 ± 0.005	3
Gas diffusion component	- 0.3 ± 0.3	-
Salt gradient power plant	0.083 ± 0.007	-
Total net power	3.1 ± 0.3	3

Figure 26 summarizes the model results for a theoretical CHPM-plant taking in the Reykjanes brine at a flow rate of 100 L/s and a temperature of 150°C. The plant cools down the brine to 50°C. The main metals extracted are iron, copper, bromide and zinc. Besides, both the Au and Ag are extracted by electrolysis and gas diffusion metal precipitation. For a production of 7000 h per year, the amount of Au removed from the brine amounts to 20 kg. For Ag, the annual production is estimated at 200 kg.

The energy demand for metal extraction is of the order of 0.6 MW. This reduces to electrical power output of the plant by about 17%. Adding salt gradient power will add about 2% to the electrical power output.

Model results for Reykjanes, Iceland

Figure 26. Summary of the model results for a theoretical CHPM-plant based on the characteristics of the Reykjanes brine.

5.2 Landau brine scenario

The stratigraphy of Landau area in upper Rhine Graben, southwest Germany, consist of Buntsandstein of lower Triassic age and the Basement (granite and mainly gneisses). The production well is 3291 m deep (true vertical depth) (Weber et al., 2016) with a production rate of 40 L/s and wellhead temperature of $\sim 159^{\circ}\text{C}$. The electricity production is 13.2 GWh/a and heat production 3 GWh/a (Agemar et al., 2014). The borehole heat exchanger in Landau at 800 m depth is used for space heating. The utilized fluid is very salty, 100,000 mg/L, with pH around 5.3.

The distribution of the input parameters and metal concentrations from the Landau site can be found in Table 11. The salinity and pH value of the input brine are given uniform distribution. The temperature of the input brine and flow rate are given triangular distributions. Histograms of 10,000 random realizations of these input value distributions can be seen in Figure 27.

The electrolytic metal extraction component (No. 3 in Figure 1) extracts the metals arsenic and copper. The amount of metal extraction in mg/L is listed in Table 12 along with the metal extraction rates in g/s. The histograms showing the probability distributions of the amount of extracted metals are shown in Figure 28. Table 13 shows the amount of extracted and extraction rate of metals for the gas diffusion electrolysis component (No. 4 in Figure 1). Histograms of probability distribution of the top four extracted metals by the gas diffusion component is shown in Figure 29.

The electric power and heat power production or consumption of each component is broken down in Table 14, along with net electric power and heat power for the whole CHPM plant. The corresponding histograms for power production or consumption of each component and of the whole CHPM loop are shown in Figure 30.

Figure 27. Probability distributions for the input parameters for the Landau brine: (a) salinity, (b) temperature, (c) flow rate and (d) pH. The distributions were constructed from 10,000 random realizations of the input parameters.

Table 11. Input parameters representing brine from the Landau geothermal area.

Parameter			Minimum value	Most likely value	Maximum value
Temperature	t	[°C]	115	123	159
Pressure	p	[bar]	1.68	2.17	6.00
Acidity/Basicity	pH	[-]	5.15	-	5.4
Flow rate	q	[L/s]	30	40	45
Salinity	s	[g/L]	97.0	-	108.5
Chloride	Cl	[mg/L]	58411	-	65900
Sodium	Na	[mg/L]	26250	-	28400
Calcium	Ca	[mg/L]	7035	-	9230
Potassium	K	[mg/L]	3480	-	4210
Strontium	Sr	[mg/L]	383	-	502
Bromine	Br	[mg/L]	191	-	219
Lithium	Li	[mg/L]	159	-	172

Iron	Fe	[mg/L]	23.5	-	156
Magnesium	Mg	[mg/L]	-	90.5	-
Boron	B	[mg/L]	19.9	-	68.8
Silicon	Si	[mg/L]	51.3	-	51.3
Fluorine	F	[mg/L]	-	35.5	-
Rubidium	Rb	[mg/L]	-	20.5	-
Manganese	Mn	[mg/L]	-	20.2	-
Arsenic	As	[mg/L]	7.25	-	15.7
Tin	Sn	[mg/L]	-	3.68	-
Zink	Zn	[mg/L]	-	3.68	-
Lead	Pb	[mg/L]	-	0.65	-
Aluminium	Al	[mg/L]	0.04	-	0.43
Nickel	Ni	[mg/L]	-	0.057	-
Copper	Cu	[mg/L]	-	0.044	-
Cadmium	Cd	[mg/L]	-	0.03	-
Mercury	Hg	[mg/L]	-	0.0005	-

Figure 28. Probability distributions of metal extractions by the electrolysis component from the Landau brine for (a) Arsenic and (b) Copper.

Table 12. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the electrolysis component from the Landau brine for arsenic and copper.

Metal		Mean extraction per volume of brine [mg/L]	Mean metal extraction rate [g/s]
Arsenic	As	9.7 ± 0.2	0.37 ± 0.09
Copper	Cu	0.038 ± 0.001	0.0014 ± 0.0001

Figure 29. The four most extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Landau brine: (a) Strontium, (b) Bromine, (c) Lithium, and (d) Iron.

Table 13. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Landau brine.

Metal		Mean extraction per volume of brine [mg/L]	Mean metal extraction rate [g/s]
Strontium	Sr	230 ± 80	9 ± 3
Bromine	Br*	100 ± 60	4 ± 2
Lithium	Li	50 ± 20	2.1 ± 0.6
Iron	Fe*	40 ± 30	2 ± 1
Boron	B*	20 ± 20	0.9 ± 0.6
Fluorine	F*	20 ± 10	0.7 ± 0.4
Rubidium	Rb	0.9 ± 0.5	0.03 ± 0.02
Manganese	Mn	15 ± 2	0.6 ± 0.1
Arsenic	As	0.4 ± 0.2	0.017 ± 0.007
Zink	Zn	2.2 ± 0.7	0.09 ± 0.03
Lead	Pd*	0.3 ± 0.2	0.013±0.007
Aluminium	Al	0.2 ± 0.1	0.009 ± 0.004
Nickel	Ni	0.03 ± 0.01	0.0011 ± 0.0004
Copper	Cu*	0.003 ± 0.002	0.00013 ± 0.00008
Cadmium	Cd*	0.015 ± 0.009	0.0006 ± 0.0003
Mercury	Hg*	0.0003 ± 0.0001	0.00001 ± 0.000006

*No extraction measurements available, extraction fraction is produced from a uniform distribution from 0% to 100%.

Figure 30. Resulting distributions for the Landau site: (a) the power input for the electrolysis component, (b) the power output of the geothermal power plant, (c) the power input for the gas diffusion component, (d) the power output of the salt gradient power component, and (e) the net electric power balance of the whole CHPM system.

Table 14. Mean power produced or consumed by components in CHPM plant for the Landau site.

Component	Mean electric power produced/consumed [MW _e]	Thermal power produced [MW _{th}]
Electrolysis component	-0.12 ± 0.04	-
Geothermal power plant	1.3 ± 0.1	3.0
Gas diffusion component	- 0.6 ± 0.5	-
Salt gradient power plant	0.084 ± 0.008	-
Total net power	0.7 ± 0.5	3.0

Figure 31 summarizes the model results for a CHPM-plant taking in the Landau brine at a flow rate of 40 L/s. The production temperature varies between 115 and 159°C. The plant cools down the brine to 50°C. The main metals extracted are Sr, Br, Li and Fe. For a production of 7000 h per year, the amount of Li removed from the brine amounts to 50,000 kg. Besides, the plant would extract about 9,800 kg of As, 40,000 kg of Fe, 100,000 kg of Br and 230,000 kg of Sr from the brine.

The energy demand for metal extraction is of the order of 0.7 MW. This reduces to electrical power output of the plant by about 54%. Adding salt gradient power will add about 6% to the electrical power output.

Model results for Landau, Germany

Figure 31. Summary of the model results for a theoretical CHMP-plant based on the characteristics of the Landau brine.

5.3 Balmatt brine scenario

Two wells, 3608 and 3830 m true vertical deep, MOL-GT-01(-S1) and MOL-GT-02, were drilled in 2015 and 2016 in the Campine Basin in the municipality of Mol in north-eastern part of Belgium. The stratigraphic unit is of Early Carboniferous age and has according to Berckmans and Vandenberghe (1998) the potential of extractable geothermal heat of 13×10^{18} J. The lithology is a sedimentary sequence of predominantly limestone and dolomite. The name Balmatt refers to the old industrial site where the wells are located. The geothermal project is part of the reconversion of the brownfield of Balmatt industries.

The geothermal reservoir is located at 3200-3600 m depth. Production temperature is up to 128°C. The geothermal fluid is Na(Ca)Cl brine with total dissolved solids (TDS) up to 165,000 mg/L (Table 15). Sodium and chloride are the main ions or up to 90% with minor amounts of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^+ , and SO_4^{-2} and Fe up to 800 mg/l (Bos and Laenen, 2017). The gas content is $\sim 2.5 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{m}^3$ geothermal fluid. Components are CO_2 75 - 80% by vol., methane 8-11%, nitrogen 2-4% and hydrogen $\sim 11\%$.

The distribution of the input parameters and metal concentrations from the Landau site can be found in Table 15. The pH value of the input brine is given uniform distributions. The salinity, temperature and the flow rate of the input brine are given triangular distributions. Histograms of 10,000 random realizations of these input value distributions can be seen in Figure 32.

The electrolytic metal extraction component (No. 3 in Figure 1) extracts only copper from the Balmatt brine. The amount of extracted copper in mg/L is listed in Table 16 along with the metal extraction rates in g/s and Figure 33 shows the histogram of the probability distribution of the extracted copper. Table 17 shows the amount of extracted metals and extraction rates for the gas diffusion electrolysis component (No. 4 in Figure 1). Histograms of probability distribution of the top four extracted metals by the gas diffusion component is shown in Figure 34.

The electric power and heat power production or consumption of each component is broken down in Table 18, along with net electric power and heat power for the whole CHPM plant. The corresponding histograms for power production or consumption of each component and of the whole CHPM loop are shown in Figure 35.

Figure 32. Probability distributions for the input parameters for the Balmatt brine: (a) salinity, (b) temperature, (c) flow rate and (d) pH. The distributions were constructed from 10,000 random realizations of the input parameters.

Table 15. Input parameters representing brine from the Balmatt geothermal area.

Parameter	Minimum value	Most likely value	Maximum value
Temperature t [°C]	115	121	123
Pressure p [bar]	1.68	2.04	2.17
Acidity/Basicity pH [-]	5.2	-	5.6
Flow rate q [L/s]	16	40	50
Salinity s [g/L]	163.5	168.7	178.3
Chloride Cl [mg/L]	94600	102457	109000
Sodium Na [mg/L]	35000	48643	54000
Calcium Ca [mg/L]	6770	9390	11000
Potassium K [mg/L]	2570	2909	3190
Iron Fe [mg/L]	445	687	809
Magnesium Mg [mg/L]	436	590	660
Strontium Sr [mg/L]	396	419	450

Bromine	Br	[mg/L]	134	142	153
Silicon	Si	[mg/L]	40	45.6	50.9
Barium	Ba	[mg/L]	14.2	16.1	17
Manganese	Mn	[mg/L]	5.4	8.9	13.6
Fluorine	F	[mg/L]	0.88	4.43	7.76
Zinc	Zn	[mg/L]	3.09	3.15	6.175
Aluminium	Al	[mg/L]	1.7	1.89	2.1
Lead	Pb	[mg/L]	0.1	0.134	0.2
Chromium	Cr	[mg/L]	-	0.0936	-
Copper	Cu	[mg/L]	0.015	0.0154	0.03
Cadmium	Cd	[mg/L]	-	0.0132	-
Nickel	Ni	[mg/L]	-	0.0035	-

Figure 33. Probability distributions of metal extraction by the electrolysis component from the Balmatt brine for copper.

Table 16. Mean values for the amount of extracted metal by the electrolysis component from the Balmatt brine for copper.

Metal		Mean extraction per volume of brine [mg/L]	Mean metal extraction rate [g/s]
Copper	Cu	0.017 ± 0.003	0.0006 ± 0.0002

Figure 34. The four most extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Balmatt brine: (a) Iron, (b) Strontium, (c) Bromine, and (d) Barium.

Table 17. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Balmatt brine.

Metal		Mean extraction per volume of brine [mg/L]	Mean metal extraction rate [g/s]
Iron	Fe*	300 ± 200	11 ± 7
Strontium	Sr	220 ± 80	8 ± 3
Bromine	Br*	70 ± 40	3 ± 2
Barium	Ba	10 ± 2	0.4 ± 0.1
Manganese	Mn	7 ± 2	0.24 ± 0.07
Fluorine	F*	2 ± 1	0.08 ± 0.06
Zinc	Zn	3 ± 1	0.09 ± 0.04
Aluminium	Al	1.8 ± 0.2	0.06 ± 0.02
Lead	Pd*	0.07 ± 0.04	0.003 ± 0.002
Chromium	Cr*	0.05 ± 0.03	0.002 ± 0.001
Cadmium	Cd*	0.007 ± 0.004	0.0002 ± 0.0001
Copper	Cu*	0.002 ± 0.001	0.00005 ± 0.00004
Nickel	Ni	0.0018 ± 0.0007	0.00006 ± 0.00003

*No extraction measurements available, extraction fraction is produced from a uniform distribution from 0% to 100%.

Figure 35. Resulting distributions for the Balmatt site: (a) the power input for the electrolysis component, (b) the power output of the geothermal power plant, (c) the power input for the gas diffusion component, (d) the power output of the salt gradient power component, and (e) the net electric power balance of the whole CHPM system.

Table 18. Mean power produced or consumed by components in CHPM plant for the Balmatt site.

Component	Mean electric power produced/consumed [MW _e]	Thermal power produced [MW _{th}]
Electrolysis component	-0.00016 ± 0.00006	-
Geothermal power plant	2.2 ± 0.5	6.8
Gas diffusion component	- 3 ± 3	-
Salt gradient power plant	0.6 ± 0.1	-
Total net power	0 ± 3	6.8

Figure 36 summarizes the model results for a CHPM-plant taking in the Balmatt brine at a flow rate of 40 L/s. The production temperature is 121°C. The plant cools down the brine to 50°C. The main metals extracted are Fe, Sr, Br and Ba. For a production of 7000 h per year, the amount of Fe removed from the brine amounts to 1055 ton. Besides, the plant would extract about 775 tons of As, 245 tons kg of Br and 35 tons of Ba per year. Metal extraction would consume the entire power production of the organic Rankine unit. Adding salt gradient power will increase power generated from the brine from about 2.2 MW to 2.8 MW.

Model results for Balmatt, Belgium

Figure 36. Summary of the model results for a theoretical CHMP-plant based on the characteristics of the Balmatt brine.

5.4 Cornwall brine scenario

The first geothermal power project in the United Kingdom is in west Cornwall and consist of two wells, a production well (4500 m deep) and an injection well (2500 m deep). The drilling started in November 2018. The chosen target was the Porthtowan Fault (PTF) which is a >15 km long NNW-SSE oriented complex strike-slip fault zone 200–500 m wide, now forming the Gornubian granitic batholith. The batholith is associated with high levels of polyphase metallic mineralisation (Ledingham et al., 2019). The reservoir fluid is estimated to be about 190°C (see D1.2 Figure 8) and its estimated composition is shown in Table 19 (Smedley et al., 1989).

The distribution of the input parameters and metal concentrations from the Cornwall site can be found in Table 19. The pH value of the input brine is given a uniform distribution. The salinity, temperature and the flow rate of the input brine are given triangular distributions. Histograms of 10,000 random realizations of these input value distributions can be seen in Figure 37.

The electrolytic metal extraction component (No. 3 in Figure 1), extracts only copper from the Cornwall brine. The amount of extracted copper in mg/L is listed in Table 20, along with the metal extraction rates in g/s and Figure 38 shows the histogram of the probability distribution of the extracted copper. Table 21 shows the amount of extracted metals and extraction rates for the gas diffusion electrolysis component (no 4 in Figure 1). Histograms of probability distribution of the top four extracted metals by the gas diffusion component is shown in Figure 39.

The electric power and heat power production or consumption of each component is broken down in Table 22, along with net electric power and heat power for the whole CHPM plant. The corresponding histograms for power production or consumption of each component and of the whole CHPM loop are shown in Figure 40.

Figure 37. Probability distributions for the input parameters for the Cornwall brine: (a) salinity, (b) temperature, (c) flow rate and (d) pH. The distributions were constructed from 10,000 random realizations of the input parameters.

Table 19. Input parameters representing brine from the Cornwall geothermal area.

Parameter	Minimum value	Most likely value	Maximum value
Temperature t [°C]	167	175	179
Pressure p [bar]	7.33	8.89	9.76
Acidity/Basicity pH [-]	5.4	-	7.7
Flow rate q [L/s]	20	40	60
Salinity s [g/L]	9.2	10.75	14.1
Chloride Cl [mg/L]	5628	6631	8750
Sodium Na [mg/L]	1890	2216	3210
Calcium Ca [mg/L]	1070	1464	1920
Potassium K [mg/L]	63.2	98.9	138
Lithium Li [mg/L]	54.4	68.2	97.2
Magnesium Mg [mg/L]	29.5	58.5	110
Strontium Sr [mg/L]	17.6	25.9	31.6
Silicon Si [mg/L]	14.4	16.2	19.6
Boron B [mg/L]	5.9	8.06	12.2

Manganese	Mn	[mg/L]	2.58	4.31	6.68
Caesium	Cs	[mg/L]	2.6	3.86	6.56
Iron	Fe	[mg/L]	1.82	3.25	5.22
Rubidium	Rb	[mg/L]	1.06	1.84	3.26
Aluminium	Al	[mg/L]	0.4	2.2	6
Barium	Ba	[mg/L]	0.51	0.65	0.87
Zinc	Zn	[mg/L]	0.1	0.3	15.5
Copper	Cu	[mg/L]	0.1	0.2	1.52

Figure 38. Probability distributions of metal extraction by the electrolysis component from the Cornwall brine for copper.

Table 20. Mean values for the amount of extracted metal by the electrolysis component from the Cornwall brine for copper.

Metal	Mean extraction per volume of brine [mg/L]	Mean metal extraction rate [g/s]
Copper Cu	0.4 ± 0.3	0.02 ± 0.01

Figure 39. The four most extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Cornwall brine: (a) Lithium, (b) Strontium, (c) Boron, and (d) Manganese.

Table 21. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Cornwall brine.

Metal		Mean extraction per volume of brine [mg/L]	Mean metal extraction rate [g/s]
Lithium	Li	6 ± 7	0.3 ± 0.3
Strontium	Sr	13 ± 5	0.5 ± 0.2
Boron	B*	4 ± 3	0.2 ± 0.1
Manganese	Mn	3.4 ± 0.8	0.14 ± 0.04
Caesium	Cs*	2 ± 1	0.07 ± 0.05
Iron	Fe*	2 ± 1	0.07 ± 0.05
Rubidium	Rb	0.09 ± 0.05	0.003 ± 0.002
Aluminium	Al	3 ± 1	0.11 ± 0.05
Barium	Ba	0.4 ± 0.1	0.017 ± 0.005
Zinc	Zn	3 ± 3	0.1 ± 0.1
Copper	Cu*	0.04 ± 0.04	0.002 ± 0.002

*No extraction measurements available, extraction fraction is produced from a uniform distribution from 0% to 100%.

Figure 40. Resulting distributions for the Cornwall site: (a) the power input for the electrolysis component, (b) the power output of the geothermal power plant, (c) the power input for the gas diffusion component, (d) the power output of the salt gradient power component, and (e) the net electric power balance of the whole CHPM system.

Table 22. Mean power produced or consumed by components in CHPM plant for the Cornwall site.

Component	Mean electric power produced/consumed [MW _e]	Thermal power produced [MW _{th}]
Electrolysis component	-0.005 ± 0.004	-
Geothermal power plant	2.3 ± 0.5	3.4
Gas diffusion component	- 0.08 ± 0.06	-
Salt gradient power plant	0.008 ± 0.002	-
Total net power	2.2 ± 0.5	0

Figure 41 summarizes the model results for a CHPM-plant taking in the Cornwall brine at a flow rate of 40 L/s. The production temperature is 175°C. The plant cools down the brine to 50°C. The main metals extracted are Sr, Li, B, Mn and Cs. For a production of 7000 h per year, the amount of Li removed from the brine amounts to 7,500 kg. The Sr production would be around 12,500 kg per year, B production 5,000 kg per year, Mn production 3,500 kg per year and Cs production about 1,750 kg per year.

Metal extraction would consume 0.085 MW of electricity. This is about 4% of the predicted power output of the organic Rankine cycle. Salt gradient power would add about 8 kW of power output to the plant.

Model results for Cornwall, England

Figure 41. Summary of the model results for a theoretical CHMP-plant based on the characteristics of the Cornwall brine.

5.5 Romanian brine scenario

The Eastern edge of the Pannonian Basin at the Apuseni Mts. is the most significant geothermal resource area of Romania. Existing wells exploiting mostly Triassic carbonate aquifers at 800–2400 m depth produce waters of 50–85°C (or 70–105°C at Oradea) at the wellhead. The compositions of the two fluid samples used in the CHPM projected are shown in Table 23. The pH is 7.9 and 8.2 with SO₄ as one of the main component (1100 mg/L) in one of the samples and two orders of magnetite less in the other one (60 mg/L). Ca concentrations are ~305 and 51 mg/L and Mg concentration ~85 and 20 mg/L, respectively.

The distribution of the input parameters and metal concentrations from the Romanian site can be found in Table 23. The salinity and the pH value of the input brine is given a uniform distribution. The temperature and the flow rate of the input brine are given triangular distributions. Histograms of 10,000 random realizations of these input value distributions can be seen in Figure 42.

The electrolytic metal extraction component (No. 3 in Figure 1) extracts only copper from the Romanian brine. The amount of extracted copper in mg/L is listed in Table 24, along with the metal extraction rates in g/s and Figure 43 shows the histogram of the probability distribution of the extracted copper. Table 25 shows the amount of extracted metals and extraction rates for the gas diffusion electrolysis component (No. 4 in Figure 1). Histograms of probability distribution of the top four extracted metals by the gas diffusion component is shown in Figure 44.

The electric power and heat power production or consumption of each component is broken down in Table 26, along with net electric power and heat power for the whole CHPM plant. The corresponding histograms for power production or consumption of each component and of the whole CHPM loop are shown in Figure 45.

Figure 42. Probability distributions for the input parameters for the Romanian brine: (a) salinity, (b) temperature, (c) flow rate and (d) pH. The distributions were constructed from 10,000 random realizations of the input parameters.

Table 23. Input parameters representing brine from the Romanian geothermal area.

Parameter	Minimum value	Most likely value	Maximum value
Temperature t [°C]	115	140	165
Pressure p [bar]	1.68	2.04	2.17
Acidity/Basicity pH [-]	7.9	-	8.2
Flow rate q [L/s]	40	55	65
Salinity s [g/L]	4.86	-	16.7
Calcium Ca [mg/L]	2040	-	12144
Magnesium Mg [mg/L]	498	-	2081
Strontium Sr [mg/L]	42	-	714
Sodium Na [mg/L]	278	-	680
Potassium K [mg/L]	226	-	500
Barium Ba [mg/L]	4.4	-	11.1
Silicon Si [mg/L]	1.8	4	4.8
Zinc Zn [mg/L]	0.1	-	4.05

Chloride	Cl	[mg/L]	2.5	-	5.0
Iron	Fe	[mg/L]	0.5	1.1	2.7
Manganese	Mn	[mg/L]	0.05	-	2.2
Rubidium	Rb	[mg/L]	1.2	-	1.37
Aluminium	Al	[mg/L]	0.27	-	1.19
Lithium	Li	[mg/L]	0.23	-	0.9
Copper	Cu	[mg/L]	0.06	-	0.51
Caesium	Cs	[mg/L]	0.31	-	0.33

Figure 43. Probability distribution of metal extraction by the electrolysis component from the Romanian brine for copper.

Table 24. Mean values for the amount of extracted metal by the electrolysis component from the Romanian brine for copper.

Metal	Mean extraction per volume of brine [mg/L]	Mean metal extraction rate [g/s]
Copper Cu	0.2 ± 0.3	0.013 ± 0.006

Figure 44. The four most extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Romanian brine: (a) Strontium, (b) Barium, (c) Zinc, and (d) Iron.

Table 25. Mean values for the amount of extracted metals by the gas diffusion component from the Romanian brine.

Metal	Mean extraction per volume of brine [mg/L]	Mean metal extraction rate [g/s]
Strontium Sr	200 ± 100	11 ± 7
Barium Ba	5 ± 2	0.26 ± 0.09
Zinc Zn	1.3 ± 0.8	0.07 ± 0.05
Iron Fe*	0.7 ± 0.5	0.04 ± 0.03
Manganese Mn	0.8 ± 0.5	0.04 ± 0.03
Aluminium Al	0.7 ± 0.3	0.04 ± 0.01
Lithium Li	0.08 ± 0.08	0.004 ± 0.004
Rubidium Rb	0.05 ± 0.03	0.003 ± 0.002
Copper Cu*	0.02 ± 0.02	0.0011 ± 0.0009

*No extraction measurements available, extraction fraction is produced from a uniform distribution from 0% to 100%.

Figure 45. Resulting distributions for the Romanian site: (a) the power input for the electrolysis component, (b) the power output of the geothermal power plant, (c) the power input for the gas diffusion component, (d) the power output of the salt gradient power component, and (e) the net electric power balance of the whole CHPM system.

Table 26. Mean power produced or consumed by components in CHPM plant for the Romanian site.

Component	Mean electric power produced/consumed [MW _e]	Thermal power produced [MW _{th}]
Electrolysis component	-0.003 ± 0.002	-
Geothermal power plant	1.6 ± 0.4	2.67
Gas diffusion component	- 6 ± 9	-
Salt gradient power plant	0.01 ± 0.004	-
Total net power	-4 ± 9	2.67

Figure 46 summarizes the model results for a CHPM-plant taking in the Romanian brine at a flow rate of 55 L/s. The input temperature is 140°C. The plant cools down the brine to 50°C. The main metals extracted are Sr, Ba, Zn, Fe and Cu. For a production of 7000 h per year, the amount of Cu removed from the brine is about 300 kg. The annual production of Sr would be around 280,000 kg, of Ba 7,000 kg, of Zn 1,800 kg and of Fe 1,200 kg.

The organic Rankine cycle is estimated to have a net power output of 1.6 MW. The average number for electric power consumption of metal extraction is 6 MW. This is about 375% of the predicted power output of the organic Rankine cycle. Salt gradient power would add about 10 kW of power output to the plant. Note though that the power consumption of the gas diffusion component has very large standard deviation for this scenario.

Model results for Romanian brine scenario

Figure 46. Summary of the model results for a theoretical CHMP-plant based on the characteristics of the Romanian brine.

5.6 Sensitivity analysis

Via the Monte Carlo method we have made a rudimentary sensitivity analysis for each scenario in the following way. For each scenario a fixed parameter list p_f is chosen where the average value is used for each of the parameters. This list of fixed parameters is then iterated and in each iteration the parameter in question is given a constant distribution that ranges $\pm 10\%$ from the average value while the other parameters remain fixed. For this new version of the parameter list p_s we run the Monte Carlo model. We thereby can estimate the range of change in electric power generation or usage that results in varying each parameter in the parameter list, i.e. estimate the sensitivity of the model results to variation of each parameter. A pseudocode of the process is shown in Figure 47.

```
pf = Dictionary of parameters with fixed average values
for parameter in pf:
    ps = pf
    ps[ parameter ] = Range of uniform distribution  $\pm 10\%$  around average

    Run MonteCarloLoop(ps)

    Save distributions for energy, heat and metal recovery
```

Figure 47. Pseudocode of the sensitivity analysis.

In Figure 48 to Figure 52 the result of the sensitivity analysis of the outputs in response to variation of the initial CHPM input parameters is presented for each component. The fixed averaged values are based on the Landau brine, see Table 11. For the electrolytic component (No. 3 in Figure 1) we see from Figure 48 that the electric power usages is mostly insensitive to the input parameters, except for a slight decrease as a with growing flow rate. The large scattering of points is due to internal probability distributions within the electrolytic model. Figure 49 shows the sensitivity of the electric power production of the geothermal power plant component (No. 4 in Figure 1) to the initial parameters. The power production is, as expected, increased with increasing temperature and flow rate, but decreases slightly with increased salinity. Note that no scatter of points occurs because the geothermal power plant model does not include probability distributions. The power consumption of the gas diffusion component (No. 5 in Figure 1) seems from Figure 50 to be insensitive to small changes of the input parameters, or at least the small dependence is hidden within the internal uncertainty of the model. The power output of the salt gradient power plant (No. 6 in Figure 1) is for the Landau brine sensitive to changes in the flow rate and salinity as seen in Figure 51. Finally, as seen in Figure 52, the overall power production of the CHPM process is most sensitive to flow rate and temperature, increasing with both parameters.

Figure 48. Sensitivity of the power consumption of the electrolysis component to small change in (a) pH, (b) pressure, (c) flow rate, (d) salinity, (e) temperature. The fixed parameter values are taken from the most likely or average values of the Landau scenario.

Figure 49. Sensitivity of the power production of the geothermal power plant to small change in (a) pH, (b) pressure, (c) flow rate, (d) salinity, (e) temperature. The fixed parameter values are taken from the most likely or average values of the Landau scenario.

Figure 50. Sensitivity of the power consumption of the gas diffusion component to small change in (a) pH, (b) pressure, (c) flow rate, (d) salinity, (e) temperature. The fixed parameter values are taken from the most likely or average values of the Landau scenario.

Figure 51. Sensitivity of the power production of the salt gradient component to small change in (a) pH, (b) pressure, (c) flow rate, (d) salinity, (e) temperature. The fixed parameter values are taken from the most likely or average values of the Landau scenario.

Figure 52. Sensitivity of the net power of whole CHPM loop to small change in (a) pH, (b) pressure, (c) flow rate, (d) salinity, (e) temperature. The fixed parameter values are taken from the most likely or average values of the Landau scenario.

6 Conclusions

A computer model has been developed to simulate the integrated CHPM2030 metal extraction and electricity generation system. The overall model is based on sub-models that describe mathematically the function of each of the technical surface components included in the model, which are two components for metal extraction and two for electricity generation. By combining the sub-models in an integrated system, it is made possible to create an overview of potential metal extraction and electricity generation from brine from specific geothermal fields. A probabilistic approach was used by applying Monte Carlo simulation technique to consider the uncertainties within the component models and of the input parameters, resulting in a probability distribution of the calculated output values.

The best available data from five geothermal fields in Europe has been used to demonstrate the ability of the model to predict the potential metal extraction and electricity generation from these fields. Also, the sensitivity of the results with respect to the specific field characteristics have been studied. The results are considered to be reliable, although further studies would help with validation of the model. Regarding topics for further development of the model that are outside the scope of the CHPM2030 project, these can be mentioned: (1) include a simple reservoir model, leaching agent, well simulator etc., (2) study how to upscale results from lab experiments to a pilot plant and (3) include the market aspect and economic feasibility, e.g. balance between metal and electricity production.

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Appendix A: GDEX data

Table 27. Data used in calibration of the gas diffusion electroprecipitation model.

Sample no.	PH	Temperature	Brine origin	Energy input [kWh/m ³]	Ca [mg/L]	Mg [mg/L]	Salinity [g/L]	Fe [mg/L]	Al [mg/L]	Li [mg/L]	Cu [mg/L]	Energy input [kWh/kg]	Ewe	Al out/in ratio	Li out/in ratio
1	3	20	ICELAND	0.19	1750	5	30	0	180	0	0	2.1	0.35	NA	NA
2	3	50	ICELAND	0.09	1750	5	30	0	180	0	0	5.17	0.35	NA	NA
3	3	20	BELGIUM	2.1	10000	600	30	50	0	0	15	3.4	0.35	NA	NA
4	3	50	BELGIUM	1.96	10000	600	30	50	0	0	15	11.5	0.35	NA	NA
5	3	20	ENGLAND	0.96	1000	50	30	800	0	0	0	11.4	0.35	NA	NA
6	3	50	ENGLAND	1.15	1000	50	30	800	0	0	0	26.4	0.35	NA	NA
7	7	20	LAB	0.13	0	0	30	NA	155.9	0	NA	31.75	0.35	1.000	0.000
8	7	20	LAB	1.61	0	0	30	NA	155.9	20	NA	10.5	0.35	0.992	0.091
9	7	20	LAB	1.61	0	0	30	NA	155.9	20	NA	10.5	0.35	0.990	0.094
10	7	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.996	0.120
11	7	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.994	0.120
12	7	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.995	0.119
13	7	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	1.000	0.119
14	7	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.990	0.116
15	7	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.995	0.119
16	7	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	80	NA	10.11	0.35	0.843	0.124
17	9	20	LAB	0.13	0	0	30	NA	155.9	0	NA	31.75	0.35	1.000	0.000
18	9	20	LAB	1.61	0	0	30	NA	155.9	20	NA	10.5	0.35	0.979	0.107
19	9	20	LAB	1.61	0	0	30	NA	155.9	20	NA	10.5	0.35	0.975	0.109
20	9	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	1.000	0.112
21	9	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.994	0.109
22	9	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	1.000	0.109
23	9	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	1.000	0.110
24	9	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.995	0.111
25	9	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.995	0.114
26	9	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	80	NA	10.11	0.35	1.000	0.095
27	11	20	LAB	0.13	0	0	30	NA	155.9	0	NA	31.75	0.35	0.091	0.000
28	11	20	LAB	1.61	0	0	30	NA	155.9	20	NA	10.5	0.35	0.893	0.149
29	11	20	LAB	1.61	0	0	30	NA	155.9	20	NA	10.5	0.35	0.896	0.149
30	11	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.798	0.248
31	11	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.794	0.246
32	11	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.798	0.249
33	11	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.797	0.246
34	11	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.794	0.246
35	11	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.1	0.35	0.795	0.249
36	11	20	LAB	1.63	0	0	30	NA	155.9	80	NA	10.11	0.35	0.802	0.120
37	7	20	LAB	2.31	0	0	30	NA	233.9	20	NA	10.2	0.35	1.000	0.020
38	9	20	LAB	2.31	0	0	30	NA	233.9	20	NA	10.2	0.35	1.000	0.089
39	11	20	LAB	2.31	0	0	30	NA	233.9	20	NA	10.2	0.35	0.936	0.208
40	7	20	LAB	3.43	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	22.32	0.7	0.903	0.251
41	7	20	LAB	4.71	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	29.95	0.9	0.926	0.246
42	9	20	LAB	3.43	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	22.32	0.7	0.994	0.057
43	9	20	LAB	4.71	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	29.95	0.9	0.994	0.074
44	11	20	LAB	3.43	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	22.32	0.7	0.777	0.120

45	11	20	LAB	4.71	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	29.95	0.9	0.737	0.177
46	7	20	LAB	2.31	0	0	5	NA	155.9	40	NA	15.21	0.35	1.000	0.021
47	7	20	LAB	1.41	0	0	75	NA	155.9	40	NA	8.61	0.35	0.948	0.233
48	7	20	LAB	1.28	0	0	135	NA	155.9	40	NA	7.59	0.35	0.964	0.233
49	9	20	LAB	2.31	0	0	5	NA	155.9	40	NA	15.21	0.35	0.990	0.145
50	9	20	LAB	1.41	0	0	75	NA	155.9	40	NA	8.61	0.35	1.000	0.285
51	9	20	LAB	1.28	0	0	135	NA	155.9	40	NA	7.59	0.35	1.000	0.373
52	11	20	LAB	2.31	0	0	5	NA	155.9	40	NA	15.21	0.35	0.953	0.368
53	11	20	LAB	1.41	0	0	75	NA	155.9	40	NA	8.61	0.35	0.606	0.244
54	11	20	LAB	1.28	0	0	135	NA	155.9	40	NA	7.59	0.35	0.560	0.238
55	7	20	LAB	2.97	2000	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	19.04	0.35	0.894	0.229
56	7	20	LAB	2.59	15000	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	15.39	0.35	0.987	0.246
57	9	20	LAB	2.97	2000	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	19.04	0.35	0.987	0.089
58	9	20	LAB	2.59	15000	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	15.39	0.35	0.987	0.318
59	11	20	LAB	2.97	2000	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	19.04	0.35	0.877	0.097
60	11	20	LAB	2.59	15000	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	15.39	0.35	0.915	0.352
61	7	20	LAB	2.28	0	100	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	12.61	0.35	0.985	0.382
62	7	20	LAB	12.19	0	1000	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	66.21	0.35	0.985	0.307
63	7	20	LAB	3.08	2000	100	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	17.23	0.35	0.995	0.342
64	7	20	LAB	12.22	2000	1000	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	83.36	0.35	0.980	0.075
65	9	20	LAB	2.28	0	100	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	12.61	0.35	0.985	0.357
66	9	20	LAB	12.19	0	1000	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	66.21	0.35	0.985	0.065
67	9	20	LAB	3.08	2000	100	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	17.23	0.35	0.985	0.332
68	9	20	LAB	12.22	2000	1000	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	83.36	0.35	0.980	0.055
69	11	20	LAB	2.28	0	100	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	12.61	0.35	0.829	0.246
70	11	20	LAB	12.19	0	1000	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	66.21	0.35	0.985	0.075
71	11	20	LAB	3.08	2000	100	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	17.23	0.35	0.884	0.176
72	11	20	LAB	12.22	2000	1000	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	83.36	0.35	0.980	0.085
73	7	50	LAB	1.69	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.66	0.35	0.995	0.103
74	9	50	LAB	1.69	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.66	0.35	0	0.995
75	11	50	LAB	1.69	0	0	30	NA	155.9	40	NA	10.66	0.35	0	0.541
76	9	20	ROMANIA	10.26	303	85.6	1.55	NA	NA	0.129	NA	0.04	0.35	388.6	NA
77	11	20	ROMANIA	10.26	303	85.6	1.55	NA	NA	0.129	NA	0.04	0.35	388.6	NA
78	9	20	ROMANIA	16.86	50.8	5.76	0.15	NA	0.044	0.033	NA	0.05	0.35	56.56	0.000
79	11	20	ROMANIA	16.86	50.8	5.76	0.15	NA	0.044	0.033	NA	0.05	0.35	56.56	0.060

Table 28: Concentrations and extraction ratios of metals other than Li and Al in the Romanian brine samples as presented in deliverable 3.2.

Sample no.	Sr [mg/L]	Sr out/in ratio	Mn [mg/L]	Mn out/in ratio	Ba [mg/L]	Ba out/in ratio	Rb [mg/L]	Rb out/in ratio	As [mg/L]	As out/in ratio	Zn [mg/L]	Zn out/in ratio	Ni [mg/L]	Ni out/in ratio
76	12.04	0.245	0.039	0.623	0.032	0.453	0.016	-	0.0038	0.297	0.0029	0.170	0	-
77	12.04	0.415	0.039	0.868	0.032	0.580	0.016	-	0.0038	0.382	0.0029	0.472	0	-
78	0.65	0.448	0.000	-	0.081	0.577	0.014	0	0.0057	0.124	0.062	0.915	0.012	0.239
79	0.65	0.995	0.000	-	0.081	0.945	0.014	0.070	0.0057	0.219	0.062	0.876	0.012	0.761

Appendix B: Model distribution around each sample

Following are the distributions that are used in Figure 15, Figure 16, Figure 17, and Figure 18.

Figure 53. Distributions of calculated energy per kg of extracted metal in kWh/kg and measured energy values of extracted of metal for each sample. These distributions are also shown in Figure 15.

Figure 54. Distributions of calculated ratios of Al metal extracted and measured values for each sample. These distributions are also shown in Figure 16.

Figure 55. Distributions of calculated ratios of Li metal extracted and measured values for each sample. These distributions are also shown in Figure 17.

Figure 56. Uniform distributions of calculated ratios of Sr, Mn, Ba, As, Zn, Rb, and Ni extracted and measured values for each sample. These distributions are also shown in Figure 18.